

> DESIRE6G <

D5.2: Report on Evaluation Results and Initial Proof-of-Concept Demonstrations

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Abstract

Deliverable D5.2, presents the evaluation results and initial PoC demonstrations within the DESIRE6G project. It presents the final testbed setup, final demo execution plan, and final data set collection, while also reporting on the first integrated D6G solution based on the initial version of components and applications provided by WP3 and WP4.

The document highlights the current status of PoCs utilizing D6G Release 1 components, emphasizing integration efforts and experimental validation across multiple testbeds. It provides insights into deployment, execution, and KPI assessments, focusing on latency, reliability, and scalability.

The document main inputs are:

- Deployment and integration of DESIRE6G Release 1 components across global and local testbeds.
- Results from PoC demonstrations, evaluating key performance indicators (KPIs) like latency, reliability, and scalability.
- Insights into refining the DESIRE6G architecture for future phases.

These results lay the path for the planned advanced demonstrations in the project's Y3.

Keywords

Use Cases Analysis, demonstrators, testing and validation, evaluation, integration, tests, PoCs demonstrations

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Table of Contents

Abstract	4
Executive Summary	17
1. Introduction	19
2. Final Testbeds Design	21
2.1. Global Testbeds	23
2.1.1. 5TONIC.....	23
2.1.1.1. Description.....	23
2.1.1.2. Overview of Integrated Components.....	27
2.1.1.3. Integration and Validation Timeline	31
2.1.2. ARNO.....	31
2.1.2.1. Description.....	31
2.1.2.2. Overview of Integrated Components.....	35
2.1.2.3. ARNO Integration and Validation Timeline.....	37
2.1.3. Federation of ARNO and 5TONIC	37
2.2. Local Testbeds	39
2.2.1. NPT-Budapest: Network Programmability Testbed.....	39
2.2.2. DLT-back Mutual Attestation and Runtime Monitoring Testbed.....	39
2.2.3. Technology & Automation LAB.....	41
3. Use Cases Analysis	44
3.1. Analysis of Use Cases Supported by the DESIRE6G Platform	44
3.2. Use Cases' Updated KPI Assessment	47
3.2.1. AR/VR (demo1).....	47
3.2.2. Digital Twin (demo2).....	48

4 Use Case Validation	50
4.1. Integration and Functional Validation of Components	50
4.2. Integration Results.....	51
5. Preliminary Demonstrators	57
5.1. Description of AR with Perceived Zero Latency Demonstrators	57
5.1.1. Introduction, Testbed and Components	57
5.1.2. Goal of the Demonstrator.....	58
5.1.3. Implementation of the AR application.....	59
5.1.4. Demonstration Startup and Workflows.....	59
5.2. Description of Real-time Digital Twin Demonstrators	64
5.2.1. Introduction, Testbed and Components.....	64
5.2.2. Goal of the Demonstrator.....	66
5.2.3. Demonstration Startup and Workflows.....	66
5.3. Proof-of-Concepts (POCs).....	71
5.3.1. Intelligent Image Monitoring.....	72
5.3.1.1. Intelligent Image Monitoring - Test and Results.....	73
5.3.2. ML Assisted RIS Configuration Based on FL	76
5.3.2.1. ML Assisted RIS Configuration - Experimental Setup	77
5.3.2.2. ML Assisted RIS Configuration - Tests and Results.....	77
5.3.2.3. Insights into the Deployment.....	78
5.3.3. Low Overhead Runtime Integrity Verification.....	79
5.3.3.1. Test Results.....	84
5.3.4. Software Performance Monitoring by Selected Code Block Trampoline Applied to L2Fwd NF.....	85

5.3.4.1. Software Performance Monitoring by Selected Code Block Trampolining Applied to L2Fwd NF - Test and Results.....	86
5.3.5. In-band Telemetry and Control.....	90
5.3.5.1 In-band Telemetry and Control - Test and Results.....	93
5.3.6 PREOF.....	94
5.3.6.1 PREOF - Test and Results.....	96
5.3.7 Lightweight Virtualization Sandboxing for Cloud Native Workloads.....	97
5.3.7.1. Lightweight Virtualization Sandboxing for Cloud Native Workloads - Test and Results..	101
5.3.8. Deployment of Secure Machine Learning Pipelines for Near-Real-Time Control of 6G Network Services	103
5.3.9. MAS and Telemetry for Service Operation Demo.....	112
6. Final Demo Execution Plan for Individual DESIRE6G Components	121
6.1. Demo 1 Intelligent and Resilient VR/AR Application with Perceived Zero Latency	121
6.1.1. Goal of the demonstrator	123
6.2. Demo 2 Real-time Digital Twins	125
7. Updated data set collection.....	129
7.1. ML-based Assisted SLA Decomposition.....	130
7.1.1. General Dataset Description	130
7.1.2. Attributes, Variable Type and Description.....	131
7.2. Elastic Scaling	131
7.2.1. General Dataset Description.....	131
7.2.2. Attributes, Variable Type and Description.....	133
7.3. Packet-based Time Series	133
7.3.1. General Dataset Description.....	133

7.3.2. Attributes, Variable Type and Description.....	134
7.4. Baseline Performance and MAS reaction to network anomalies in Demo 1	135
7.4.1. General Dataset Description.....	135
7.4.2. Attributes, Variable Type and Description.....	135
7.5. Digital Twin App.....	136
7.5.1. General Dataset Description.....	136
7.5.2. Attributes, Variable Type and Description.....	137
7.6. DLT Network Transactions.....	137
7.6.1. General Dataset Description.....	137
7.6.2. Attributes, Variable Type and Description.....	138
7.7. ML assister RIS configuration at EDGE nodes	139
7.7.1. General Dataset Description.....	139
7.7.2. Attributes, Variable Type and Description.....	140
8. Tests Definition and results	142
8.1. Definition of Tests for Use Case Validation	142
8.1.1. Definition of Tests for Demo 1 Y2.....	142
8.1.2. Definition of Tests for Demo 2 Y2.....	154
9. Conclusion	164
10. References	165

List of Figures

Figure 1 5TONIC Testbed Used for Demo2 in Y2 Preliminary Demonstration.....	24
Figure 2. Unitree Go1 System Architecture Overview.....	25
Figure 3. Unitree Go1 Robot Setup (A) and ASUS RT-AX89X Wi-Fi 6 Access Point (B).....	25
Figure 4. DESIRE6G Site Cluster: Distributed DT Application and Kubernetes Configuration.....	28
Figure 5. High-level Workflow of the DT Application. (A) The remote operator hand gestures are captured via webcam and sent to the gesture control app. (B) The gesture control app recognizes gestures and generates control commands. (C) The robot sends state feedback for real-time synchronization with its virtual replica.....	30
Figure 6. ARNO+UPC Testbed Used for Demo 1 in Y2 Preliminary Demonstration.....	32
Figure 7. 5G User Equipment Modem (A) and Radio Unit USRP N310 (B).....	33
Figure 8. Distributed AR Application.....	35
Figure 9. ARNO-5TONIC DLT-based Federated Testbed Layout.....	38
Figure 10. DLT-backed Mutual Attestation Testbed Components.....	40
Figure 11. PREEF-DETNET Environment.....	42
Figure 12. PREEF-DETNET Devices.....	43
Figure 13. PREEF-DETNET Testing Equipment.....	43
Figure 14. RAN Deployment: D-RAX dashboard.....	60
Figure 15. GRAFANA dashboard of the RIC.....	61
Figure 16. Demo 1 Workflow 0 (Steady State).....	62
Figure 17. Demo 1: Workflow 1.....	63
Figure 18. Demo 1: Workflow 2.....	64
Figure 19. Demo 2 Y2: Api Endpoint For Dt Service Deployment Via So.....	67
Figure 20. Demo 2 Y2: Dt Service Graph Structure.....	68
Figure 21. Demo 2 Y2: Key Functionalities of The Dt Application.....	69
Figure 22. Demo 2: DT service Traffic management in a congested network scenario.....	71
Figure 23. Experimental Setup Of Intelligent Image Monitoring.....	72
Figure 24. Robot Trajectory in the Industrial Area Covered by Four Ip Cameras.....	73

Figure 25. The Method Helps to Meet the Throughput Budget on the Critical Link.....	74
Figure 26. Architecture of Image Monitoring Poc After the Integration with Iml And Smo	75
Figure 27. The Traffic Flow Across Different Network Functions.....	76
Figure 28.. Overview of Federated Learning Architecture Integration with 5tonic (Phase 4).....	77
Figure 29. Convergence of Algorithms: (Top) Test Accuracy, (Bottom) Training Loss.....	79
Figure 30. Overview of the Spread over Time Hashing Process to Measure Integrity.....	81
Figure 31. Generic Testbed over L2fwd Network Function.....	85
Figure 32.. Representation of Different Code Block Entries.....	86
Figure 33. . Normal Execution Program Behaviour vs. Stressed Execution Program.....	88
Figure 34.. Stress Level Depending on Call Frequency of Reference Block.....	89
Figure 35. Telemetry Header	91
Figure 36. Experimental Setup of In-Band Telemetry and Control.....	91
Figure 37. INT Dashboard indicating change of path due to congestion.....	94
Figure 38. Preof-detnet in DESIRE6G.....	95
Figure 39. Logical PReOF-DEtNET scenario.....	96
Figure 40. Traditional vs sandboxed containers paradigm	98
Figure 41. Container runtime design	99
Figure 42. Application deployment workflow.....	100
Figure 43. DESIRE6G Architecture for Secure Distributed Intelligence.....	103
Figure 44. MAS pipeline deployment with initial mutual attestation.....	105
Figure 45. WRapping request.....	106
Figure 46. Set Agent’s Credentials Request.....	107
Figure 47. Multi-Step Remote Attestation UI.....	108
Figure 48. Remote Attestation UI.....	109
Figure 49. Traffic Measurements and Agent’s Total Messages.....	110
Figure 50. Experimental testbed.....	111
Figure 51. Illustrative Example of MAS and Telemetry for service operation.....	112
Figure 52. Federated Testbed Setup for the Demonstration.....	113
Figure 53. SPIRENT Testcenter Interface	115

Figure 54. Near-real-time operation workflow to be demonstrated.....	117
Figure 55. Selected exchanged messages.....	117
Figure 56. Delay measurements with congestion.....	119
Figure 57. Delay measurements after flow reconfiguration.....	120
Figure 58. Demo 1 Final setup.....	122
Figure 59. Demo 2 final setup.....	126
Figure 60. Ground truth and sample points.....	131
Figure 61. Vehicular traffic dataset of turin.....	132
Figure 62. The testbed used to collect the packet based delay time series.....	134
Figure 63. Example visualization of LiDAR data captured in ROS bag for the DT app dataset.....	137
Figure 64. RIS Environments.....	140
Figure 65. Packet Capture at the P4 collector that shows the summary of 16 INT reports.....	147
Figure 66. Latency of the monitored flow on two paths.....	151
Figure 67. Increase in the Latency on the Primary Path.....	152
Figure 68. Demo 2 Y2: Bandwidth Utilization for DT App traffic in Baseline POC.....	156
Figure 69. Demo 2 Y2: RTT Latency Distribution for DT App Traffic in Baseline POC.....	157
Figure 70. Demo 2 Y2: Generated Background Traffic Bandwidth on Grafana.....	160
Figure 71. Demo 2 Y2: TM Policies for Critical Traffic Prioritization in the DT Service.....	161
Figure 72. Demo 2 Y2: Latency Distribution For DT App Traffic Under Network Congestion –Comparison Of Soa (A) And D6G Platform (B).....	162

List of Tables

Table 1. DESIRE6G Components.....	21
Table 2. 5TONIC Integration and Validation Timeline.....	31
Table 3. ARNO Integration and Validation Timeline.....	37
Table 4. Overview of DESIRE6G Use Cases.....	45
Table 5. DESIRE6G KPI Mapping to Demonstrators and PoCs.....	49
Table 6. Integration of DESIRE6G Components (WP3 & WP4) Status January 2024.....	53
Table 7. Integrated Components in Demo1 Y2.....	57
Table 8. Integrated Components in Demo2 Y2.....	65
Table 9. Demo 2 Y2: Monitored Ros Topics For Robot-Dt Communication.....	70
Table 10. Prime Program Results – Calculation Of 1000 Prime Numbers.....	82
Table 11. Prime Program Results -Calculation Of 100000 Numbers.....	82
Table 12. Prime Program Results -Calculation Of 1 000 000 Prime Numbers.....	83
Table 13. Results of a Patched Binary when Under Stress* Compared to the Same Patched Binary Running For The Same Time In Normal Conditions.....	88
Table 14. Web-server Workload.....	101
Table 15. Key-value Store Workload.....	102
Table 16. Demo 1 Intelligent and Resilient VR/AR Applications with Perceived Zero Latency Workflows	124
Table 17. DESIRE6G Overview of Updated Data Set Attributes.....	129
Table 18. ML-based assisted SLA decomposition Attributes, Variable Type and Description.....	131
Table 19. Elastic Scaling, Variable type and Description.....	133
Table 20. Packet-based time Attributes, Variable Type and Description.....	134
Table 21. Baseline Performance and MAS reaction to network anomalies Attributes, Variable Type and Description.....	135
Table 22. DLT Network Transactions Attributes, Variable Type and Description.....	138
Table 23. Heterogeneous RIS Environments Attributes, Variable Type and Description.....	141

List of Acronyms

5G	5th Generation Mobile Network
ACK	Acknowledgement
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AP	Access Point
API	Application Programming Interface
AQM	Active Queue Management
AR	Augmented Reality
BMv2	Behavioural Model version 2
CF	Call Frequency (metric)
CI	Continuous Integration
CLI	Command Line Interface
CN	Core Network
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CRI-O	Kubernetes Container Runtime Interface
CU	Centralized Unit
C-V2N	Cellular Vehicle-to-Network
DETNET	Deterministic Networking
DL	Distributed Ledger
DLT	Distributed Ledger Technology
DPU	Data Processing Unit
DPDK	Data Plane Development Kit
dRAXtm	Accelleran RAN Dashboard
DT	Digital Twin
DU	Distributed Unit
ECDF	Empirical Cumulative Distribution Function
ET	Execution Time (metric)
EVIM	Enhanced Virtual Infrastructure Manager
FL	Federated Learning
FPGA	Field-Programmable Gate Array

Geth	Ethereum Go Implementation
GRE	Generic Routing Encapsulation
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
HW	Hardware
I/O	Input/Output
IML	Infrastructure Management Layer
INFLUXDB	Time Series Database
INT	In-band Network Telemetry
IP	Internet Protocol
IRM	Invariant Risk Minimization
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LiDAR	Light Detection and Ranging
MAS	Multi-Agent Systems
ML	Machine Learning
NF	Network Function
NIKSS	P4 eBPF Backend
NFR	NF Routing
NFV	Network Function Virtualization
NFVO	Network Function Virtualization Orchestrator
NIKSS	New INDIKNOW Stratum Switch
NS	Network Slice
ORIN	NVIDIA Jetson ORIN Board
P4	Programming Protocol-Independent Packet Processors
PDP	Policy Decision Point
PoC	Proof of Concept
PPV-TM	Per Packet Value Traffic Manager
PPV-TM	Perception, Planning, and Virtualization for Traffic Management
PX4	Drone Flight Control Software
QoS	Quality of Service
ODL	OpenDaylight SDN Controller

OLI	Optical Line System
OSM	Open-Source MANO (Management and Orchestration)
OpenPose	Library for Pose Estimation
PoA	Proof-of-Authority (Blockchain Consensus Algorithm)
PoPs	Points of Presence
PCAP++	Packet Capture Library
PPV-TM	Per Packet Value Traffic Manager
PS	Parameter Server
QoE	Quality of Experience
QEMU	Quick Emulator
R/VR	Augmented Reality/Virtual Reality
RAN	Radio Access Network
RIC	RAN Intelligent Controller
RIS	Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces
ROS	Robot Operating System
ROS2	Robot Operating System 2
ROS bag	File format used in ROS to store messages exchanged between nodes
RRU	Radio Remote Unit
RTK	Real-Time Kinematic
RTMP	Real-Time Messaging Protocol
RTT	Round-Trip Time
RViz	ROS Visualization Tool
SHA256	Secure Hash Algorithm 256-bit
SC	Service Catalogue
SDK	Software Development Kit
SECaaS	Security as a service
SLAM	Simultaneous Localization and Mapping
SMO	Service Management and Orchestration
SMO	Service Management and Orchestration
SNPN	Split Network Processing Node
SoA	State-of-the-Art

SONiC	Software for Open Networking in the Cloud
SPO ROADM	Signal Processing Optics Reconfigurable Add-Drop Multiplexer
SW	Software
TCPROS	TCP-based ROS Communication Protocol
TM	Traffic Management
UDP	User Datagram Protocol
UE	User Equipment
UPF	User Plane Function
URLLC	Ultra-Reliable Low Latency Communications
VIM	Virtual Infrastructure Manager
VM	Virtual Machine
VNC	Virtual Network Computing
VXLAN	Virtual Extensible LAN
Wasm	WebAssembly
WiFi6	Wi-Fi 6 (802.11ax)
YOLO	You Only Look Once (Object Detection Library)

Executive Summary

This deliverable **D5.2, Report on evaluation results and initial proof-of-concept demonstrations** provides an overview of the progress made in evaluating key technologies and validating early-stage implementations within the DESIRE6G project. The document highlights experimental efforts focused on integrating project components, deploying distributed testbeds, and conducting proof-of-concept (PoC) demonstrations to assess the practical feasibility of the proposed solutions.

The report outlines the setup and validation of both global and local testbeds, as well as the establishment of federated testbeds that enable collaborative experimentation across multiple sites. These testbeds form the foundation for evaluating critical 6G technologies, with an emphasis on achieving low latency, high reliability, and flexible service management in distributed environments.

Throughout the second year of the project, DESIRE6G partners conducted several demonstrations that showcased the potential of emerging 6G use cases. These include the deployment of Augmented Reality (AR) applications with ultra-low latency requirements and the implementation of Digital Twin (DT) systems for industrial automation and monitoring. In addition, a series of PoCs explored advanced functionalities such as intelligent telemetry, network optimization using AI, and secure data processing pipelines.

Key contributions of this deliverable include:

- Enhanced Testbed design: designs and configurations for global testbeds (5TONIC and ARNO) and the federation with local testbeds, ensuring integration of DESIRE6G components.
- PoC Demonstrations: Execution of initial PoC demonstrations.
- Final Datasets and Demo Execution Plan: Compilation of final datasets and the finalized execution plan for upcoming Y3 demonstrations.
- Evaluation Framework: Development and refinement of an evaluation framework for assessing KPIs, such as latency, reliability, and resource efficiency, across testbed environments.
- Test Results: Preliminary results from PoC demonstrations, highlighting the integration of DESIRE6G components.
- The deliverable also outlines the challenges encountered during integration and testing, along with the solutions implemented to address these issues.

This deliverable represents an important step in the project's roadmap, as it provides practical evidence supporting the feasibility of the proposed 6G solutions. The outcomes from these stage evaluations will inform further development phases and guide the upcoming Y3 demonstrations, ensuring that the project continues to advance toward its goal of delivering innovative and resilient network solutions for the next generation of 6G technologies.

1. Introduction

In the DESIRE6G project, Work Package 5 (WP5) focuses on integrating, validating, and experimentally evaluating key technological components developed within the project. These efforts rely on distributed testbeds, where real-world experimentation helps evaluate the feasibility, scalability, and reliability of the proposed 6G architecture.

This deliverable, D5.2, builds on the groundwork done in D5.1, which defined the initial testbed setup and integration plans. At this stage, the focus is on evaluating DESIRE6G Release 1 components, assessing their deployment in test environments, and analyzing their performance against KPIs. The results from these experiments will guide further refinements and contribute to the project's next phase of demonstrations, that are planned to be presented in next deliverable D5.3 Final report on evaluation results and initial proof-of-concept demonstrations.

Document section overview

Section 2 provides an overview of the testbeds used in this phase, including the 5TONIC and ARNO global sites, as well as several local and federated setups. The testbeds offer a controlled environment for deploying DESIRE6G components, running experiments, and validating performance metrics. This section also touches on the integration timelines and the collaborative efforts involved in setting up these sites across different locations.

Section 3 provides an overview of the use cases supported by the project, showing how the DESIRE6G platform addresses the needs of applications like AR and DT systems. The section also includes an updated analysis of the KPIs defined in the project.

Section 4 digs into the functional validation process, with the outline of individual DESIRE6G components are tested and integrated into the various testbeds. The section highlights both successes and challenges encountered during the integration process, ensuring transparency in how these technologies perform under real-world conditions.

Section 5 presents POCs demonstrations conducted during this phase of the project. These PoCs highlight the project's ability to support use cases like AR applications with perceived zero latency and

DT systems. Each PoC is described in terms of its hardware and software components, the integration process, and its execution plans.

Section 6 looks into the next steps in the project, outlining a demonstration roadmap for the third year of the project.

Section 7 describes the final datasets for DESIRE6G components and PoCs, expanding on previous deliverable D5.1 with updates on data collection, attributes, and structure.

In Section 8, the deliverable outlines the testing framework and evaluation results from the PoC demonstrations. Performance metrics, including latency, throughput, and reliability, are assessed to determine whether the solutions meet the project's KPIs. This section provides a clear picture of the DESIRE6G platform's capabilities at this stage of development.

Finally, **Section 9** closes up the document with current findings and next steps. The conclusion outlines the path forward for integrating additional components, conducting final demonstrations, and continuing the validation process to ensure that DESIRE6G technologies remain aligned within the project's goals and with the evolving demands of future 6G networks.

2. Final Testbeds Design

This section describes the different test sites that are involved in the experimental evaluation of the project for Year 2 and Year 3. It highlights the technologies and infrastructures to be integrated in each site, distinguishing between *global*, *local*, and *federated* testbeds. Global testbeds are large-scale sites that host both the DT and the AR/VR main use cases of the project. Local testbeds, in contrast, are smaller-scale setups that will be used for DESIRE6G individual component development and validation. Federated testbeds enable collaborative and dynamic utilization of distributed resources across the DESIRE6G, allowing interoperability, scalability, and innovation in deployment environments.

Table 1 provides the identified high-level DESIRE6G macro-components that will be developed in the local testbeds and later integrated into the global testbeds and the representative PoCs.

TABLE 1. DESIRE6G COMPONENTS

DESIRE6G component	Local testbed	Global testbed (ARNO: Demo 1, 5TONIC: Demo 2)	PoC
SMO/Service Orchestrator	Service and Management Orchestrator (SMO) testbed	ARNO, 5TONIC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lightweight Virtualization Sandboxing Intelligent Image Monitoring
IML	NPT-Budapest	ARNO, 5TONIC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Intelligent Image Monitoring
MAS	UPC testbed	ARNO, 5TONIC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Deployment of Secure Machine Learning

			Pipelines for Near-Real-Time Control of 6G Network Services <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mas and Telemetry for Service Operation
BHT / SECaaS	TSS DLT-back mutual attestation and runtime monitoring testbed	ARNO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low Overhead Runtime Integrity Verification • Software Performance Monitoring by Selected Code Block Trampolining • Deployment of Secure Machine Learning Pipelines for Near-Real-Time Control of 6G Network Services
RAN accelerated components	OPENLAB	None	
DLT federation	None	5TONIC	None

SOL	None	ARNO, 5TONIC	None
Pervasive monitoring	ARNO	ARNO, 5TONIC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In-band telemetry and control • MAS and Telemetry
PREOF	TID	5TONIC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PREOF

2.1. Global Testbeds

2.1.1. 5TONIC

2.1.1.1. Description

This section provides details of the 5TONIC testbed (Madrid, Spain) configuration, used for the preliminary Y2 demonstration 2 (Demo 2, Real-time Digital Twins) and evaluation, performed as part of the first integration phase involving D6G software release R1 components. A complete overview of the testbed and the available hardware/software resources was reported in D5.1 [1].

FIGURE 1 5TONIC TESTBED USED FOR DEMO2 IN Y2 PRELIMINARY DEMONSTRATION

The testbed configuration, illustrated in Figure 1, is designed to support advanced experimentation and analysis of the DT use case. It includes the Unitree Go1 quadruped robot paired with a Mini PC featuring an Intel N100 Processor, 12GB RAM, 256GB disk storage, and an Intel Wi-Fi 6 (AX200) wireless network adapter. Please note that the robot's native stack operates as a pre-configured application distributed across several internal modules, all interconnected through an Ethernet switch (see Figure 2). The main modules of the Unitree Go1 robot and their respective roles are described as it follows:

- **Motion Control Board (Raspberry Pi):** This module serves as the robot central processing unit, coordinating and handling high-level control tasks. It enables whole-body movement commands, including velocity and orientation adjustments.
- **Main Control Board (MCU):** The MCU is responsible for low-level motion control and manages precise locomotion by executing commands for motor positions, velocities, and torques in each leg.
- **Sensing Motherboards (3x NVIDIA Jetson Nano):** These boards are dedicated to processing data from various onboard sensors.

FIGURE 2. UNITREE GO1 SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE OVERVIEW

FIGURE 3. UNITREE GO1 ROBOT SETUP (A) AND ASUS RT-AX89X WI-FI 6 ACCESS POINT (B)

Communication with these modules is facilitated by the manufacturer Software Development Kit (SDK) package (i.e., *unitree_legged_sdk*) via User Datagram (UDP) protocol. However, this SDK introduces

compatibility challenges with the DT application, which requires messages in Robot Operating System (ROS) [2] format, the widely adopted open-source software standard for most robotic applications. Moreover, installing or modifying software on the robot internal boards is not recommended, as it may disrupt the native stack and compromise the robot operation.

To address these challenges, a mini-PC is mounted on the robot and connected to the internal switch (see Figure 3-A), extending its local computing capabilities and enabling the integration of additional components, such as light detection and ranging (LiDAR) and camera, as well as the ROS wrapper to facilitate communication between the DT application and the robot internal modules. This Mini PC also serves as a User Equipment (UE), providing high-speed connectivity to the robot via a Wi-Fi 6 Access Point (AP). The AP model used in this setup is the ASUS RT-AX89X (see Figure 3-B), linked to a programmable switch – specifically the Edgecore DCS801 with 32 QSFP28 100 GbE ports – creating a network backbone that extends to the 5TONIC data center.

The data center comprises various computing resources, as illustrated in Figure 1, with the following roles and hardware specifications:

- **Edge Server 1:** A bare-metal server (Dell PowerEdge R630) equipped with 128GB RAM, 2x Intel Xeon E5-2620 CPUs, and an NVIDIA GeForce RTX 2080 Ti GPU. It hosts the Infrastructure Management Layer (IML) layer and the DT application, which leverages the open-source robot simulator NVIDIA Isaac Sim [3]. It is important to note that the Isaac Sim platform has strict minimum requirements, including Ubuntu 18.04 Operating System (OS), an Intel Core i7 or AMD Ryzen 5 CPU, 16GB of RAM, 50GB of disk storage, and a GeForce RTX 2070 GPU with NVIDIA drivers (version 473.47).
- **Edge Server 2:** A Virtual Machine (VM) configured with 4GB RAM, 4 CPUs, and 200GB disk storage. It hosts the SMO component as part of the Intent-based Orchestration DESIRE6G layer. The SMO is responsible for overseeing orchestration and lifecycle management of Application Functions (AFs) and Network Functions (NFs) for the DT service, while providing guidelines to the IML for their deployment.
- **Traffic Generator:** A VM with 12GB RAM, 8 CPUs, and 50GB disk storage. This VM runs on a server directly connected to the programmable switch and is responsible for generating diverse traffic

flows, simulating realistic and dynamic network conditions. It is important to note that this virtualized approach was adopted due to server availability constraints in the 5TONIC data center. For the final demo, a bare-metal server will be used to achieve optimal performance.

2.1.1.2. Overview of Integrated Components

This section presents an overview of the components integrated into the testbed, detailing their role within the system.

DT Application

The testbed implements a distributed Digital Twin (DT) application that combines advanced robotic, simulation, and communication technologies. The DT application is fully containerized and deployed as Deployments/Services within a Kubernetes cluster at the D6G edge site, as illustrated in Figure 4. This approach provides multiple advantages, including consistency, portability, environment isolation, scalability, and automation. The key components of the DT application include:

- **ROS Master:** Manages naming and registration services for all modules in the DT system, enabling seamless communication between ROS-based components. The current implementation uses ROS1, combining melodic and noetic distributions for compatibility across different components.
- **Digital Twin:** Provides a virtual replica of the physical robot using the Isaac Sim platform, accurately replicating its behaviour in real time. The demo utilizes the Isaac Sim 2023.1.0 release, running efficiently on Edge Server 1 with GPU acceleration via the NVIDIA Container Toolkit [4] ensuring realistic physics simulation.
- **Go1 Base:** Provides a ROS interface for interacting with the robot stack. In the demo, the interaction is performed in high-level control mode, allowing commands to control the robot full-body movements, such as adjusting velocity and orientation.
- **Gesture Control App:** Enables remote control of the robot through hand gestures, using camera inputs and an AI-based model converting these gestures into movement commands. In its current implementation, the application utilizes the MediaPipe Hand Landmarker model [5] from Google AI and can recognize five specific commands: stopping all motion (velocity commands

set to zero), moving forward (increasing linear velocity), moving backward (decreasing linear velocity), turning right (increasing angular velocity), and turning left (decreasing angular velocity).

- **LiDAR:** Provides ROS drivers for a laser scanner device to support environment mapping. The model employed is the SLAMTEC RPLIDAR A3¹, a 360-degree laser scanner offering a range of up to 25 meters, a scanning frequency of up to 20 Hz, and millimeter-level accuracy, designed for high-performance mapping and navigation in dynamic environments.
- **Camera:** Provides ROS drivers for an external camera, allowing the visualization of the robot perspective. The model employed is the Orbbec3D Astra camera², which is equipped with a depth sensor that combines high-definition RGB imaging with advanced depth sensing. In the demo, it is used exclusively as an RGB camera, transmitting raw video data.
- **SLAM:** Integrates simultaneous localization and mapping (SLAM) algorithms in order to generate maps of environments using data from robot sensors (i.e., LIDAR, odometry). The application leverages Cartographer [6] algorithm, which allows precise location tracking and navigation for the robot.

FIGURE 4. DESIRE6G SITE CLUSTER: DISTRIBUTED DT APPLICATION AND KUBERNETES CONFIGURATION

¹ <https://www.slamtec.com/en/LiDAR/a3>

² <https://store.orbbec.com/products/astra-1>

The cluster is built on the K3s [7] Kubernetes distribution and comprises two nodes: Edge Server 1, which acts as the K3s server, and the robot (Mini PC), functioning as the K3s agent. The Go1-base, LiDAR, and camera modules run on the robot, while the other applications operate on the edge. Pod-to-pod communication is managed using Virtual Extensible LAN (VXLAN) network virtualization technology with the Flannel CNI plugin [8].

Please note that in a ROS system, nodes need to know the IP address of the ROS Master to establish network communication. However, since the IP address of the ROS Master container is dynamically assigned at deployment in Kubernetes, a Headless Service is used. This service enables application pods to resolve the ROS Master hostname via DNS, using the service name that maps to the corresponding application pods, ensuring seamless communication.

Figure 5 provides a high-level overview of the DT application operation, conceptualized in a smart factory scenario where a remote operator interacts with the system from a different location. The operator can control the robot using hand gestures, view its virtual replica in real time, monitor its camera feed, and track its position through SLAM algorithms that generate maps from LiDAR data. The workflow includes:

1. **Gesture input** (see Figure 5-A): The operator hand gestures are captured through a webcam and sent to the gesture control app.
2. **Gesture recognition and command generation** (see Figure 5-B): The artificial intelligence in the gesture control app processes the webcam feed, recognizes the operator gestures, and converts them into control commands. These commands are sent downstream at a predefined control-loop frequency to the robot stack, instructing it to perform specific movements.
3. **State feedback and real-time synchronization** (see Figure 5-C): The robot executes the received commands and continuously sends upstream its operational state data (i.e., joint states, LiDAR readings, odometry, camera feeds, etc) back to the DT application. As the robot moves, its actions are mirrored in real-time within the virtual environment, while the operator simultaneously views a map of the surroundings and the robot video feed.

FIGURE 5. HIGH-LEVEL WORKFLOW OF THE DT APPLICATION. (A) THE REMOTE OPERATOR HAND GESTURES ARE CAPTURED VIA WEBCAM AND SENT TO THE GESTURE CONTROL APP. (B) THE GESTURE CONTROL APP RECOGNIZES GESTURES AND GENERATES CONTROL COMMANDS. (C) THE ROBOT SENDS STATE FEEDBACK FOR REAL-TIME SYNCHRONIZATION WITH ITS VIRTUAL REPLICA.

2.1.1.3. Integration and Validation Timeline

TABLE 2. 5TONIC INTEGRATION AND VALIDATION TIMELINE

Planned deadline	Planned integration & validation task
Q4 - 2023	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Integration of hardware and software components
Q1 - 2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Set up the basic network infrastructure. Deployment of the DT use case Conduct baseline experiments
Q2 - 2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Deployment of DESIRE6G components inside 5TONIC resources Conduct experiments
Q3 - 2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Integration of the DESIRE6G components in the DT use case Preliminary demonstration (Y2 demo)
Q2 - 2025	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Validation of final DESIRE6G components within the 5TONIC test site
Q4 - 2025	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Final demonstration of integrated DESIRE6G solution for the DT use case (Y3 demo)

2.1.2. ARNO

2.1.2.1. Description

In this section we present the configuration setup for the preliminary Y2 demonstration 1 (Demo 1, AR with perceived zero-latency) and assessment carried on during the first integration phase involving the D6G software release R1 components. The general testbed description and the available physical resources have been reported along with all the hardware/software availability details in D5.1 [1]. For the preliminary demonstration goals (demo 1), and to fully enable the functionalities of the MAS subcomponents utilized in the demonstration, the ARNO testbed is federated with the UPC testbed located in Barcelona (Spain). The federation is realized using a dedicated GRE (Generic Routing

Encapsulation) tunnel connectivity between two gateways provided with public IP addresses. Layer-3 subnetting is configured to enable the proper routing of packets between the two premises. The Round-Trip-Time (RTT) of the connectivity is around 30ms. This aspect needs to be considered in the test results, especially those related to the MAS reaction time. It is worth noting that the final demo will integrate the MAS agents directly in the ARNO testbed, thus removing the related delay.

FIGURE 6. ARNO+UPC TESTBED USED FOR DEMO 1 IN Y2 PRELIMINARY DEMONSTRATION

The testbed hardware configuration has been designed to enable advanced experimentation and analysis of the AR use case with an end-to-end service connectivity spanning domains of different technology: a RAN domain followed by a programmable data plane domain, connecting the RAN to an edge node.

FIGURE 7. 5G USER EQUIPMENT MODEM (A) AND RADIO UNIT USRP N310 (B)

The testbed includes a 5G UE, built around a NVIDIA Jetson ORIN board paired with a video camera and a Quectel 5G modem attached through USB-3.1 connectivity (see Figure 7-A). The ORIN board serves as the central computing unit, enabling high-performance visual data capture and processing. The video camera enables real-time multimedia acquisition, while the Quectel modem performs high-speed connectivity.

Radio Access Network (RAN)

The Radio Access Network (RAN) is implemented using most components provided by Accelleran and integrated into the ARNO testbed, offering a high-performance and programmable platform for radio signal processing and data transmission. The Radio Unit (RU) consists of the USRP 310N device, equipped with four radio channels connected using unconfined coaxial cables to mitigate external frequency interference (see Figure 7-B). The RU interfaces with the Distributed Unit (DU) through a 10GbE fiber connection.

The DU runs the Accelleran DU software version 1.0.2, hosted on Server S1 (Dell PowerEdge R760) featuring an Intel Xeon Gold 6438Y+ CPU with 128 cores, 256 GB RAM, and Ubuntu Linux with a low-latency kernel (v5.15). The Centralized Unit (CU), including both CU-CP (Control Plane) and CU-UP (User Plane) components, operates on Server S2. S2 features an identical hardware configuration as S1 but runs a standard Ubuntu kernel (v5.15).

The DU and CU are interconnected using a 100GbE interface. Server S2 also hosts the Accelleran RIC version 7.2.0, enabling intelligent RAN management, and the Open5GS Core Network (CN) version 2.7.1,

which performs end-to-end 5G connectivity towards the Data Net (in this case a programmable packet-optical network).

Programmable Packet-Optical Network

Complementing the RAN, the testbed integrates a Programmable Packet-Optical Network, powered by a combination of P4 switches such as BMv2 and NIKSS, deployed on Dell servers. These switches are connected using 100GbE interfaces, enabling programmable data forwarding and packet processing. Additionally, an optical bypass is implemented using a pair of Ericsson SPO ROADM R1 and R2, equipped with PM-QPSK 100Gb/s coherent cards with tuneable wavelengths. At the edge between the RAN and the programmable packet-optical network, node N1 is realized as a combination of two P4 switches and a Juniper router. This N1 node is realized to create a real queue congestion in the Juniper router and collect the packet latency information.

Two-Stage P4 Collector

The collected latency data have also been exploited to provide training data for the MAS agents DRL models. To enable detailed traffic analysis, the testbed features a Two-Stage P4 Collector, enhancing packet capture and deep traffic pattern insights. This collector plays a key role in enhancing the INT Report capture and analysis, including aggregation and correlation of latency metadata from different switches and different flows. Specifically, the collector in the correlation mode receives the reports in each time window, performs latency statistics on the samples and produces a single correlation report carrying average, minimum and maximum latency. This report is sent to the MAS agent with a sampling frequency lower than the Report generation rate. In our implementation, while the report generation rate equals the traffic rate (i.e., for each flow packet a Report is generated by the sink INT node), the sampling frequency set towards the MAS agent is set to 1 second.

Additional traffic is generated and analysed using a Spirent N4U Traffic Generator and Analyzer, simulating diverse and realistic network conditions. Finally, Python-based MAS Agents deployed within the UPC cluster oversee network orchestration and management (S3).

2.1.2.2. Overview of Integrated Components

This section presents an overview of the components integrated into the testbed, detailing their role within the system.

AR Application

The testbed supports a distributed AR application conceptualized in Figure 8, which demonstrates the integration of advanced multimedia and communication technologies. The application is structured as follows:

FIGURE 8. DISTRIBUTED AR APPLICATION

- **Source Application:** The AR app runs on the NVIDIA Jetson Orin board. It captures video streams using the onboard camera and performs initial object detection using the YOLO (You Only Look Once) library [9]. YOLO applies a single neural network to the full image, segmenting it into regions and making predictions for object classes. This enables low-latency and efficient processing suitable for real-time applications.
- **Edge Application:** Once the initial data is captured, it is sent to an edge node for data fusion and secondary object detection, including 3D reconstruction. The edge application aggregates and processes additional information for enhanced object accuracy.
- **Data Streaming and Visualization:** Processed data is streamed to an Oculus Quest 3 virtual reality headset, configured in passthrough mode. The Oculus captures the surrounding

environment using its stereo cameras and overlays AR information, enabling users to visualize detected objects, even those occluded in their immediate field of view.

In its current implementation, the application leverages the YOLOv7-tiny model, pre-trained to detect up to 80 object categories. The system allows selection of desired detection categories without impacting real-time performance. The model runs efficiently on the NVIDIA Jetson ORIN module, exploiting GPU acceleration via the CUDA Toolkit [10] for optimized inference. Preliminary evaluations indicate that the system is capable of processing and streaming video at 60 frames per second (FPS), highlighting its suitability for latency-sensitive applications. The app utilizes an environment based on Linux, Unreal Engine 5.3, and NVIDIA Jetpack 5.

Key AR Features

- **Real-Time Detection:** Object detection can be performed either at the source node (ORIN) or transmitted to a cloud node for further processing.
- **3D Vision Overlay:** The Oculus headset displays enhanced AR content, including occluded object detection, leveraging Unreal Engine 5.3 for immersive rendering.
- **GPU Acceleration:** The system harnesses NVIDIA Jetson's GPU capabilities to ensure high throughput and minimal latency during object detection and streaming.
- **Customizable Performance:** The YOLO model weights can be further optimized using custom datasets tailored to the specific AR application requirements.

The combination of high-speed 5G connectivity, advanced hardware resources, and AI-driven AR processing makes this application a viable solution for real-world deployments requiring real-time object detection, immersive visualization, and robust network performance. It is worthwhile to note that this is a preliminary version of the AR application, as described as use case in D2.1 and demonstrator in D5.1. Specifically, the preliminary version includes just one camera at the user equipment and only the forward chain is implemented (i.e., backward control via the Oculus is not implemented yet). Moreover, in this demo, the user equipment is not configured for handling mobility. All such preliminary restrictions will be removed in the final demo, that will include both forward /backward chains as well as user

equipment mobility onboarded onto a drone. Future developments aim to enhance the AR application by incorporating multi-object tracking and context-aware overlays to further improve user experience.

2.1.2.3. ARNO Integration and Validation Timeline

TABLE 3. ARNO INTEGRATION AND VALIDATION TIMELINE

Planned deadline	Planned integration & validation task
Q4 - 2023	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identification of required hardware and software components
Q1 - 2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Set up the basic network infrastructure • Starting initial deployment of the AR/VR use case • Conduct baseline experiments
Q2 - 2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Starting integration of DESIRE6G components inside ARNO resources • Conduct experiments and preliminary demonstrations (Y2 demo)
Q4 - 2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Starting integration of final release components of DESIRE6G inside ARNO resources • Starting final deployment of the AR/VR use case
Q3 - 2025	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Validation of final components of DESIRE6G in ARNO
Q4 - 2025	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Final Demo of integrated DESIRE6G solution for the AR/VR use case (Y3 demo)

2.1.3. Federation of ARNO and 5TONIC

The ARNO and 5TONIC testbeds support DLT-based (i.e., blockchain and smart contracts) federation functionality from WP3 [11] enabling both sites to dynamically discover, negotiate, and establish service

federations while maintaining privacy and security. This approach is particularly beneficial for extending local capabilities and enabling collaborative deployment or management of shared workloads. The multi-domain ARNO-5TONIC federation environment is illustrated in Figure 9.

FIGURE 9. ARNO-5TONIC DLT-BASED FEDERATED TESTBED LAYOUT

Each site features a custom-built orchestrator that operates on top of cloud orchestration platforms (e.g., Kubernetes, OpenNebula), providing a shared virtualized environment for on-demand workload deployment. In order to provide DLT-based federation functionality, each site is also equipped with an Ethereum-based blockchain node, deployed as a Docker container, seamlessly integrated with its orchestrator to form a peer-to-peer blockchain network. Federation procedures are implemented and managed by a generic Federation Smart-Contract (SC), which serves as a distributed authority on the blockchain. The orchestrators interact with the Federation SC through immutable transactions that are permanently recorded on the blockchain ledger.

Basic connectivity between the two sites is pre-established through a GRE tunnel configured between the testbed gateways, utilizing L3 GARR/GEANT internet routing across university networks. To ensure traffic isolation for different services or workloads during dynamic federation deployments, dedicated Virtual Extensible LANs (VXLANs) are deployed on top of the GRE tunnel, creating separate virtual networks.

2.2. Local Testbeds

2.2.1. NPT-Budapest: Network Programmability Testbed

Two very similar testbed infrastructures were built at ERI-HU and ELTE to support the evaluation and validation of data plane algorithms and methods. Both testbeds are in Budapest a few hundred meters from each other (but connected to different external networks) and rely on several servers with different hardware accelerators, like SmartNIC, DPU, FPGA and Tofino ASIC. We started building them around five years ago with the purpose of enabling the performance evaluation of our 5G-related packet processing and QoS solutions. Over the years, the testbeds were extended with different hardware accelerators and low-cost programmable router-boards. ELTE and ERI-HU have used these testbeds in a number of recent publications in the past few years.

The testbed will be used for the development and validation of components (i.e., IML, infraNFs) needed for the operation of a single DESIRE6G site. We also realize the Intelligent Image Monitoring PoC, as described in Section 5.3.1, in this local testbed.

A more detailed description of the testbed and the available resources are found in D5.1 [1].

2.2.2. DLT-back Mutual Attestation and Runtime Monitoring Testbed

The DLT-back mutual attestation modifies the MAS agent through TSS's Security as a Service (SECaaS) server which injects the required code primitives for measuring and verifying the agent signatures as well as storing the associated signatures.

Figure 10 outlines the components deployed in the DLT-back mutual attestation and runtime monitoring testbed. Two agents belonging to a MAS are extended with proving and verifying primitives and wrapped to expose an API for mutual attestation. The testbed includes the Security-as-a-Service (SECaaS) system. All the components run in different virtual machines deployed in different servers.

FIGURE 10. DLT-BACKED MUTUAL ATTESTATION TESTBED COMPONENTS

The components that comprise the DLT-back mutual attestation and runtime monitoring testbed are:

- **Proving and verifying primitives:** Remote attestation acts as a digital trust handshake, crucial for ensuring the integrity and authenticity of network devices or agents. The process is centred around two key functions:
 - **Proving Primitive:** This component is responsible for demonstrating that the current state of an agent is secure and unaltered. It achieves this by generating a cryptographic hash of its software and configuration, which is then signed with a private key. This approach ensures that the proof is accurate and resistant to tampering. Any changes in the system would result in a different hash, signalling a possible security breach.

- **Verifying Primitive:** The verifying primitive's role is to authenticate the proof provided by the proving primitive. It does this by comparing the received hash or signature against a known, trusted value or set of values. This comparison is vital in determining whether the state of the proving primitive is intact and trustworthy.
- **DLT nodes:** Blockchain technology, in the form of Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT), particularly Ethereum, which stands as the most widely recognized blockchain platform. Ethereum offers a versatile platform capable of supporting various applications via the execution of smart contracts, which operate directly on the blockchain. We employed Go Ethereum [12] (Geth) to establish a private Blockchain network and record state of agents during the remote attestation workflow. Additionally, we have leveraged the Web3.py library [13] for seamless interaction with the Blockchain.
- **Smart contracts:** The implementation of smart contracts is interesting for ensuring that the states of all agents remain secure and trustworthy. This process maintains a continuous chain of trust, as every agent state is immutably recorded and can be reliably verified when a remote attestation is triggered. To compile and deploy smart contracts, we relied on node.js-Truffle, which simplified the development process and allowed us to efficiently integrate these contracts into our network.
- **Docker:** Virtualization technology utilized for providing flexibility and Efficiency in deploying and managing agents.
- **MAS agent:** We have further enhanced the UPC agents by introducing a python FastAPI, enabling seamless communication and interaction between agents. This API allows agents triggering the verifying and proving functions within our network.
- **PostgreSQL:** Relational database used by the SECaaS component to store measures and public key of agents provided by the measurer and the key generator.

2.2.3. Technology & Automation LAB

In the Technology & Automation Lab, PREOF-DetNet has been developed, as shown in Figure 11. This required three Tofino switches representing the Replication and Elimination components of the PREOF-DetNet algorithm, a server supporting Data Plane Development Kit (DPDK) where the Ordering

component has been implemented, and two conventional switches acting as 10G/100G speed translators. A traffic generator and disturbance equipment have also been used to test the environment.

FIGURE 11. PREOF-DETNET ENVIRONMENT

The traffic generator sends IP traffic to the 30X switch, which acts as a 10G to 100G speed translator. The IP traffic is then converted into DetNet traffic at the Tofino ingress node. This traffic is replicated across different paths towards the destination to enhance network reliability. At the Tofino egress, duplicates are discarded, and the traffic is sent to the DCSG_3, a 100G to 10G speed translator. The traffic reaches the DPDK server, which is responsible for reordering it and converting it back into IP traffic. Finally, the traffic returns to the traffic generator.

The characteristics of the equipment used are described below, along with the relevant images.

10G/100G speed translator switches

DPDK server

Tofino switches

FIGURE 12. PREOF-DETNET DEVICES

- **Two conventional switches.** One Edgecore Networks AS7315-30X switch with an Intel Atom C3508 CPU, 16GB DDR4-2400 RAM, and an M.2 SSD. Additionally, an Edgecore Networks 7316-26XB-O-AC-F switch with an Intel Pentium D1519 CPU and 2x 8GB DDR4 SO-DIMM SDRAM.
- **DPDK server.** Dell PowerEdge R510, Intel Xeon series 5500 CPU, 8 DIMM DDR3, 8TB storage.
- **Three Tofino switches.** Edgecore CSP-7550 switches, 2x Intel Xeon Gold 5218 (16-Core, 2.3 GHz), 256GB (32GB x 8), 240GB M.2 SSD, Tofino BFN-T10-064Q-B0, 32 x 100G QSFP28.

FIGURE 13. PREOF-DETNET TESTING EQUIPMENT

- **Traffic Generator.** Spirent SPT-N12U, supports up to 576 x 25G or 10G ports, 288 x 50G ports, 144 x 100G or 40G ports, 48 x 200G, or 24 x 400G Ethernet ports per chassis.
- **Disturbance equipment.** IXIA Network Emulator II, 10G/1G impairment emulation.

3. Use Cases Analysis

3.1. Analysis of Use Cases Supported by the DESIRE6G Platform

The table 4 presents an outline of the five distinct use cases within the context of the DESIRE6G project. The table highlights the functional requirements, KPIs, technical components, workloads, and infrastructure needed for five advanced AR/VR use cases: Digital Twin for Robotics, Intelligent Image Monitoring, Latency Sensitive Robot Control, and Cloud Rendered Gaming. Each use case emphasizes low-latency communication, robust edge computing, and real-time processing to ensure optimal performance. For instance, Digital Twin for Robotics prioritizes high throughput (130–960 Mbps) and reliability (99%) with enhanced 5G and edge computing infrastructure. Similarly, Latency Sensitive Robot Control demands ultra-low latency (0.5–10 ms) and high availability (99.9999%) with advanced accelerators and orchestration solutions. Cloud Rendered Gaming, while focused on delivering high-quality visuals (1080p, 30-120 FPS), also necessitates reliable bidirectional communication and GPU-based edge servers.

Across these use cases, there is a consistent need for cutting-edge communication technologies like WiFi6, 5G, and low-latency networks paired with edge computing infrastructure equipped with GPUs, DPUs, and FPGAs. Scalability varies by application, ranging from supporting 1-50 robots in robotics control to accommodating 100 sensors in image monitoring. Workloads generally involve real-time video streaming, synchronization, and secure data handling, underscoring the importance of high performance and dynamic resiliency in deployment. This convergence of technologies ensures these applications meet their stringent KPIs and functional requirements. Each use case conveys specific scenarios and technical requirements aimed at showcasing the innovative capabilities of DESIRE6G across various domains.

Table 4 shows a breakdown of the key aspects of each use case, including their descriptions, functional requirements, KPIs and technical components.

TABLE 4. OVERVIEW OF DESIRE6G USE CASES

	AR/VR Use Case	Digital Twin for Robotics	Intelligent Image Monitoring	Latency Sensitive Robot Control	Cloud Rendered Gaming
Functional Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Realtime video processing and rendering for 3D object reconstruction. • Tracking, mapping, and object recognition. • Natural user interaction with the virtual environment. • Secure bidirectional communication. • Optimization for low latency, high bandwidth, and efficiency. • Stable and continuous communication with dynamic resiliency. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support for various computing resources and real-time control. • Mobility, localization, and timing synchronization. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Real-time video quality optimization and integration with sensor data. • Minimal delay and bandwidth usage. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Real-time control with low latency and synchronization requirements. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Real-time video streaming with low latency and performance isolation.
KPIs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • End-to-end latency: <20ms (ideal), <50ms (tolerated). • Throughput: Min 130Mbps – Max 960Mbps. • Reliability: 99%. • Scalability: 1/10 drones, 100 users. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • End-to-end latency: <10ms (ideal), <100ms (tolerated). • Reliability: 99.999%. • Availability: 99.999%. • Data Rate: 1Gbps. • Scalability: 1-50 robots. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • End-to-end latency: <10ms. • Reliability: 99.99%. • Availability: 99.999%. • Data Rate: 100Mbps. • Scalability: 1-100 sensors. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • End-to-end latency: 0.5 – 10 ms. • Reliability: 99.999%. • Availability: 99.9999%. • Data Rate: 1Mbps to few Gbps. • Scalability: 1-50 robot arms. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Video quality: Min. 1080p resolution, min. 20 FPS, FPS between 30-120 in 99% of the time. • End-to-end-latency: 20-30 ms. • Reliability: 99.999% for commands, 98% for video stream.
Technical Components	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhanced 5G wireless communication. • Edge computing with GPU acceleration. RTK devices for tracking. P4 switches, GPU, FPGA, DPU. • Headset with radio interface. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WiFi6, 5G communication. • Edge computing with hardware accelerators. • Orchestration solutions. • Commodity edge servers. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WiFi6, 5G communication. • Edge computing with hardware accelerators. • Orchestration solutions. • Commodity edge servers. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low-latency communication technologies. Edge computing with accelerators. • Orchestration solutions. Commodity edge servers. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low-latency wired and wireless communication. • Edge computing with GPU. • Orchestration solutions.

					Commodity edge servers.
Workloads	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Video processing, tracking, user interaction, data sync, authentication. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sensor data transmission, control commands, real-time application functions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Realtime video transmission, selective filtering, integration with sensor data. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sensor data transmission, control commands, real-time application functions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Realtime video transmission, selective filtering, performance isolation.
Infrastructure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Edge computing infrastructure with wired connectivity. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cloud and edge computing infrastructure with radio access networks. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Edge computing infrastructure with programmable accelerators. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Edge computing infrastructure with x86based servers. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Edge computing infrastructure with GPU-based servers.

The use cases in DESIRE6G are very relevant in terms of market impact. The market size for the use cases outlined in the table reflects their growing adoption across industries. Digital Twin for Robotics, a critical tool for industrial automation and process optimization, is projected to reach a market value of over \$40 billion by 2030, fuelled by demand in manufacturing, logistics, and smart city development. Intelligent Image Monitoring, widely applied in surveillance, healthcare imaging, and autonomous systems, is part of the broader computer vision market expected to surpass \$50 billion by 2028, driven by advancements in AI and sensor technologies. Both markets rely heavily on innovations in edge computing and connectivity to deliver real-time insights and reliability.

Latency Sensitive Robot Control, integral to precision tasks like robotic surgery, factory automation, and teleoperation, aligns with the robotics market forecast to exceed \$200 billion by 2030. This segment’s growth is underpinned by the increasing adoption of robots across various sectors. Meanwhile, Cloud Rendered Gaming, part of the rapidly expanding cloud gaming market, is expected to reach over \$21 billion by 2030 as consumers seek high-quality, low-latency gaming experiences. These markets demonstrate a strong synergy with the technical requirements outlined in the table, emphasizing the demand for scalable, low-latency, and high-reliability infrastructure to support their growth.

3.2. Use Cases' Updated KPI Assessment

All the activities carried on integration and assessment of the preliminary implementations of DESIRE6G components and use cases are subject to the hardware and software constraints provided by the testbed platforms. This means that the ideal use cases KPI described in D2.1 have been reviewed, considering the constraints and a re-mapping between the ideal KPI and the achievable KPI in the demonstration phase. This re-mapping does not impact the effectiveness of the components and the overall solutions. In fact, the testbeds run legacy 5G connectivity platforms with given max performance figures. Thus, some KPI targeting extreme performance figures for applications may not be met for technological reasons.

3.2.1. AR/VR (demo1)

The end-to-end latency KPI of xR applications, in the order of 5ms for the network only, faces the minimum latency performance achieved by the Accelleran RAN, in the order of around 11ms (one-way). This KPI may be relaxed to the tolerated KPI for the end-to-end application+network latency in the order of around 50ms. It is important to note that the DESIRE6G architecture and components will be able to guarantee the stability of the latency during service runtime, and service assurance driven by the MAS will operate in the sub-second scale (near-real time reactivity). Similarly, for the bandwidth KPI, the maximum bandwidth in the uplink direction provided by the current Accelleran DU and N310 radio module configuration is around 50Mbps. This bandwidth is already achievable by real 5G or even ELTE advanced networks, but not the stable latency. The expected (ideal) bandwidth of the application is around 40Mbps. This will require a configuration fine tuning during the integration of components to reach this level of throughput in a stable way. Finally, the scalability KPI is restricted to the evaluation of one single drone and a single user (i.e., the user wearing the Oculus Headset) with multiple concurrent services emulated through synthetic traffic generation. Here, the scalability will be evaluated in terms of guaranteeing the service SLA when multiple increasing services of different priority run in the network.

3.2.2. Digital Twin (demo2)

For what concerns the KPIs of Digital Twins for robotics, they depend on the specific robotic task and the sensors involved, as outlined in D2.1. For example, a human-robot interaction scenario involving a manipulator with proximity and distance sensors requires an end-to-end latency of 1 ms, which is significantly lower than the 10-20 ms RTT latency achievable by the 5TONIC 5G RAN. In contrast, in the case of the mobile quadruped robot used in the initial Demo2, which is remotely controlled by a digital worker, the system can tolerate latencies of up to 100 ms.

Note that the digital worker interacts with the virtual replica and sends high-level remote-control commands to the robot downstream, such as position and velocity instructions, which are low-volume data. This remote control interacts with the motion control board of the robot and can operate within a control cycle of 10 ms to 100 ms. Upstream data includes low-volume information, like joint states and odometry for position estimation and high-volume camera and LiDAR streams that can consume a few Mbps of bandwidth. The expected (ideal) bandwidth of the DT application is around 50 Mbps. Regarding sensor response times, upstream flows are more latency-tolerant, with acceptable latencies ranging from 20 ms to 100 ms.

Therefore, the overall KPIs for end-to-end application and network latency can be relaxed to approximately 100 ms, with a required data rate of around 50 Mbps. Finally, the scalability KPI is limited to evaluating a single robot (i.e., Unitree Go1 quadruped model) and one user (i.e., the remote operator using the gesture-control app). Multiple concurrent services will be simulated using synthetic traffic, and the evaluation will focus on the network ability to maintain SLA guarantees as service loads and priorities increase.

The following table maps KPIs for DESIRE6G use cases to their corresponding demonstrators and proof of concepts (PoCs), highlighting critical performance metrics. It covers AR/VR, Digital Twin, and Image Monitoring use cases, comparing ideal benchmarks with WP5 demonstrator targets. Key metrics include end-to-end latency, with AR/VR targeting <20ms (5ms network latency) ideally, and Digital Twin aiming for <10ms ideally. Bandwidth requirements range from 4-960 Mbps depending on the use case, with AR/VR requiring up to 960 Mbps for downloads and Image Monitoring spanning 4-24 Mbps per camera. Reliability and availability benchmarks vary across use cases, with Digital Twin achieving the highest

reliability (99.999%) to ensure the successful transmission of control commands and sensor updates over time for precise robot-to-DT synchronization, and Image Monitoring showcasing ultra-high availability (99.9999%) to maintain uninterrupted video feeds for continuous real-time data capture and analysis. Scalability considerations span from drones and robots to cameras and nodes, reflecting diverse deployment scenarios and service requirements.

TABLE 5 DESIRE6G KPI MAPPING TO DEMONSTRATORS AND POCS

Use case (Demo)	E2E latency	Bandwidth (per flow)	Reliability	Availability	Scalability
AR/VR (Demo 1)	Ideal: <20ms (5ms for the network) WP5: <50ms (20 ms for the network)	Ideal: 50-100 Mbps (UL), 130-960 (DL) WP5: <40Mbps (UL), 100Mbps (DL)	99%	NA	Ideal: 1/10 drones, 100 users WP5: 1 drone, 1 user with emulated concurrent services (synthetic traffic)
Digital Twin (Demo 2)	Ideal: <10ms WP5: <100ms (1-20 ms for the network)	Ideal: 1Gbps WP5: <50Mbps	99.999%	99.999%	Ideal: 1-50 robots WP5: 1 robot with emulated concurrent services (synthetic traffic)
Image Monitoring (PoC)	Ideal: < 40ms (10-20ms for the network)	Ideal: 4-24Mbps per camera assuming 10-50 cameras	98-99%	99.9999% Service unavailability cases outage	Ideal: 10-50 nodes or more WP5: 1 emulated robot and 4 IP camera streams

4. Use Case Validation

4.1. Integration and Functional Validation of Components

The main goal of the integration and functional validation of various components in DESIRE6G, including AI-based solutions, within a distributed testbed environment is to ensure that the integrated system meets the requirements for low-latency and optimized performance, critical for the successful deployment of 6G technologies.

The primary objectives of the project's integration efforts include:

- **Integration and Functional Validation:** Combining software and hardware components developed in prior work packages (WP3 and WP4)
- **Deployment and Evaluation:** Deploying these components to evaluate their suitability for relevant use cases and ensure they meet key quality indicators (KQIs), including end-to-end latency.
- **Support for Use Cases:** Integrating applications pertinent to various use cases and performing functional validations to support these integrations, ensuring readiness for performance validation in subsequent tasks (T5.3).

Execution and Approach

- **Component Integration:** Following the architectural guidelines set by T2.2, the components developed in WP3 and WP4.
- **Functional Testing:** Comprehensive functional validations are conducted to ensure that the integrated solution meets the necessary performance criteria and is ready for further validation and demonstration.
- **Preliminary and Final Releases:** A preliminary release of the integrated DESIRE6G solution is targeted for month 18 with MS5.2, showcasing the first integration of selected components. This is followed by a final release at month 30 with MS5.3 incorporating the complete set of components for comprehensive evaluation.

The preliminary results from DESIRE6G integration efforts underscore the progress towards achieving the project's goals:

- **Successful Integration:** Initial integration efforts have successfully combined multiple components, demonstrating the feasibility of the DESIRE6G solution.
- **Functional Validation:** Early functional tests have validated the performance of integrated components, ensuring they meet the required KQIs.
- **Deployment on Testbeds:** Components have been deployed on the distributed testbed environment, allowing for real-world evaluation and optimization.

4.2. Integration Results

The integration work between partners has shown progress, as indicated by the completion status of various systems and their modules.

In Table 6 we see an overview of DESIRE6G's integration of components. Each subsystem (1, 2, 3, 4) is a set of connected components that work together to enable specific functionalities. These subsystems consist of modules, which handle different tasks, and interfaces, which define how they communicate.

Each subsystem plays a key role in the network and is grouped into four main categories:

1. Telemetry & Network Monitoring
2. ML for Radio Optimization
3. Service Orchestration & Network Functions
4. In-Band Telemetry & Traffic Control

Each of these four subsystem includes:

- **Modules:** The components performing specific functions.
- **Interfaces:** How they communicate (e.g., REST APIs, data exchange).
- **Commands & Messages:** The key operations for integration.
- **Integration State:** The progress of implementation.

- Testbed & PoC Mapping: Where the subsystem is deployed (5TONIC, ARNO, or UPC) and its role in demos or PoCs.

In Subsystem 1, partners successfully integrated the Telemetry Agent with the Telemetry Collector, as well as the MAS Node Agent with the P4 Switch Agent, achieving a 100% completion status for both pairs. This accomplishment lays a solid groundwork for better data collection and routing policy application, essential for managing and optimizing networks effectively. RAN integration has started in order to enable the full Accelleran RAN Open 5G release including functional split. Currently, single server deployment is working, and integration is ongoing to support the functional split version and integrate the Near Real-Time RIC xAPP with the MAS Agent using a proper interface, not yet defined. Current integration achievement is 40%.

Subsystem 2, led by UOU, introduces an initial development with the introduction of an ML Model for RIS Configuration Prediction. However, this subsystem is a standalone element where integration is not applicable.

In Subsystem 3, progress has been made in integrating the Service Orchestrator and Local NFVO/IML modules. The REST API for forwarding Service Graph in YAML format is nearly complete, reaching a 100% completion status. Similarly, the QoS Configuration API integration between Local NFVO/IML and Traffic Manager has also reached 100% completion. These advancements pave the way for more dynamic service deployment and quality-of-service management, crucial for meeting various application needs.

In Subsystem 4, progress have been made to propose and integrate the in-band control solutions with the Telemetry Collector operation in the ARNO testbed. The first stage integration has reached 100% integration and shown as working PoC at the ICTON 2024 Demo Zone (held in July 2024).

TABLE 6. INTEGRATION OF DESIRE6G COMPONENTS (WP3 & WP4) STATUS JANUAR 2024

Subsystem	Module 1	Module 2	Interfaces (Protocols, Data Models)	Integration state (%)	Testbed Integration	Target Demo/PoC
1	Telemetry Agent	Telemetry Collector	REST API to collect telemetry from a given flow	100	ARNO+UPC (federated)	AR (Demo1)
1	MAS Node Agent	P4 Switch Agent	REST API to apply a new routing policy for a given flow	100	ARNO+UPC (federated)	AR (Demo1)

1	Accelleran RAN - Open 5G SNPN	MAS Node Agent	Interaction with RIC and xAPP, deployment of RAN	40	ARNO+UPC (federated)	AR (Demo1)
2	ML assisted RIS configuration prediction based on FL	NA	<p><u>Training Phase:</u> Local nodes <-> parameter server. Local nodes host RIS controllers and respective training data. Parameter server is a VM or a container.</p> <p><u>Deployment Phase:</u> Tx <-> Local nodes, Local nodes <-> Rx, and Local nodes <-> RIS controller.</p> <p>No direct mapping to architecture components.</p>	<p>We conduct only the training phase integration.</p> <p>100%</p>	5TONIC	

3	Service Orchestrator (NUBIS)	Local NFVO/IML	REST API to forward the Service Graph, in YAML format, from the Service Orchestrator to IML (for service deployment on a DESIRE6G site)	100	5TONIC	DT (Demo2)
3	Data Lake (NUBIS)	Local NFVO/IML	REST API to expose container registry	100	5TONIC	DT (Demo2)
3	Local NFVO/IML (ELTE)	Per Packet Value Traffic Manager)	QoS Configuration API	100	5TONIC	DT (Demo2)

3	Local NFVO/IML	NF Routing	REST API to configure NF Routing data plane	100	5TONIC	DT (Demo2)
3	Local NFVO/IML	UE2Service Mapper	REST API to configure UE2Service Mapper data plane	100	5TONIC	DT (Demo2)
4	Telemetry Collector	P4 in-band control programs	Adaptation of code to support ultra-fast in-band messages related to QoS/trust change	100	ARNO	In-band telemetry and control PoC

5. Preliminary Demonstrators

5.1. Description of AR with Perceived Zero Latency Demonstrators

5.1.1. Introduction, Testbed and Components

We report the description of the preliminary demonstrator (year 2 development release) of the Augmented Reality application with perceived Zero Latency, hereafter also referred to as Demo 1 Y2. The demonstrator is hosted at the ARNO testbed and involves the collaboration of different partners. The demonstrator implements a preliminary release of the distributed AR application described as general use case in D2.1 [14] and planned demonstration in D5.1 [1]. The network deployment includes the following segments: the UE, the RAN and the programmable data plane over a packet-optical network. The Desire6G components integrated and utilized in the demo are the following: the preliminary AR application, entirely developed in WP5, the RAN software stack provided by Accelleran, the INT and postcard telemetry P4 implementations, the double stage P4 collector, the MAS. The testbed, the detailed list and software versions are fully described in Section 2.1.2. The list of the integrated software developed in the project and used in the demo is reported in the table below:

TABLE 7. INTEGRATED COMPONENTS IN DEMO1 Y2

Integrated components (Responsible Partner)	Version (WP)	D6G component (release)
MAS Agent (UPC)	C3.7 (WP3)	Yes (R1)
MLFO (UPC)	C3.6 (WP3)	Yes (R1)
Telemetry Agent (UPC)	C4.4001 (WP4)	Yes (R1)
P4 Telemetry Collector (CNIT, SSSA, NVIDIA)	C4.4002 (WP4)	Yes (R1)
In-band telemetry including UE (CNIT, SSSA)	C4.4003 (WP4)	Yes (R1)
AR distributed application (CNIT)	C5.1 (WP4)	No (R1)
RAN software stack (ACC)	N/A	No (R1)

In this demonstrator, we evaluate the e2e performance of a preliminary AR service with perceived zero latency, involving different network segments in the DESIRE6G site, including 6G RAN, programmable transport and edge cloud. Other than the rough integration of different components, this phase focuses on tuning the overall system to target relevant KPIs. The following components have been considered and integrated to work together, following top-down approach):

- MLFO: this component is adopted for the activation of MAS agent(s) according to the requirements of the service
- MAS Agent: each MAS agent is responsible for the assurance of service performance. Each agent is fed, via Telemetry agent, with data collected by the pervasive monitoring system, running algorithms for the identification of critical conditions, being able to apply policy for its adaptation.
- Pervasive Monitoring: the DESIRE6G monitoring approach is here applied to collect relevant data directly from the application traffic, leveraging INT (at the UE side and at the traversed switch) to collect heterogeneous data at forwarding and application planes.
- 6G RAN: a 6G RAN stack, encompassing functional split and software defined radio units are integrated with the programmable data plane to transmit the application traffic from the UE to the application server, running in the edge cloud.
- A preliminary AR distributed application is exploited in the integrated testbed.

5.1.2. Goal of the Demonstrator

The demonstration objectives are two-fold:

- to showcase a service-oriented end-to-end pervasive monitoring system, where actual end-to-end latency experienced by the application is monitored constantly in different technological domains, and where programmable data plane enables in-band telemetry collection of metadata.
- to demonstrate service re-optimization at near real time using the Multi Agent System concept, in charge of receiving, aggregating and analysing telemetry in a distributed way, in order to detect service level agreement violations and suggest the most appropriate countermeasures.

5.1.3. Implementation of the AR application

The forward chain of the application developed for the demo is conceptually shown in Figure 14. The source app runs on the ORIN board and includes video capture and a first object detection. Then, augmented data are sent to the edge app for further data fusion and a second detection. Final data are streamed to the Meta Oculus for 3D vision. In our current developmental phase, we leverage the YOLO library for object detection. To guarantee a real-time quality of experience it is necessary that the one-way end-to-end latency is kept under 25 milliseconds. This is the SLA assigned to the MAS for the end-to-end latency service assurance.

The use case is mapped to the preliminary application development. In this release, the source app runs object detection using the “YOLO” library version 7, while the edge app performs AI-based pose estimation resorting to the OpenPose library. The result of the artifacts introduced by the two processing stages is shown in this video performed during the last EuCNC 2024 conference³ where we invited the DESIRE6G booth visitors to wear the Oculus and try the live application.

The Oculus, a virtual reality device configured in passthrough mode, displays the area surrounding the user captured by its stereo camera, then overlays information about detected objects behind obstacles. In fact, the camera captures images to detect objects occluded in the user’s field of view.

5.1.4. Demonstration Startup and Workflows

The demo begins by showcasing the Accelleran RAN deployment. At bootstrap, the CU, the near-real-time RIC, and the CN are deployed, while the DU and the Radio Unit are managed by the RAN operator.

The dRAXtm dashboard (see the screenshot in Figure 14 provides automatic scripts to deploy all disaggregated RAN modules independently. Using a registration script, the UE is attached to the RAN, and the dashboard displays the current topology, including the connected user equipment.

³ <https://smart-networks.europa.eu/event/eucnc-6g-summit-2024/>

FIGURE 14. RAN DEPLOYMENT: D-RAX DASHBOARD

For monitoring purposes, a comprehensive Grafana section is integrated into the RIC dashboard, as shown in Figure 15. It offers a wealth of metrics, such as throughput and radio transmission quality. Statistics are available both in aggregate form and on a per-user equipment basis, enabling effective real-time monitoring of RAN performance.

FIGURE 15. GRAFANA DASHBOARD OF THE RIC

The demonstration is carried out in three different workflows. Moreover, a rich set of tests has been carried out, fully detailed and commented in Section 8.

The workflows are the following:

- Workflow 0 (steady state and congestion without MAS intervention)
- Workflow 1 (congestion at the packet-optical domain and MAS intervention)
- Workflow 2 (congestion at the RAN and MAS intervention)

In workflow 0, depicted in Figure 16, we show the steady state and the pervasive monitoring using in-band telemetry: video packets are timestamped at the UE and at the core network (CN) to obtain the RAN latency. Once entering the packet-optical domain, each node adds its hop latency to obtain the second segment latency. At N4, packet is popped to be delivered to the edge app, and a Report is generated towards the P4 collector. Packet metadata are stored and processed here. After a timeout, a stats Report message is sent to the MAS Agent that checks the SLA compliancy. The Time Pervasive Monitoring operates at the single packet level and is able to detect and localize latency deviations with the finest granularity. The MAS agents operate at near real time resorting to the telemetry statistics provided by the P4 collector at each Stats Report generation, in the order of tens of milliseconds. The

agents can identify the most appropriate countermeasures to recover the SLA requirements in case of latency deviations. In the case of workflow 0, the MAS is deactivated to show the results in terms of congestion when extra traffic is sent by the Spirent to Node N4. The tests and results are reported in Section 8.

FIGURE 16. DEMO 1 WORKFLOW 0 (STEADY STATE)

In workflow 1, shown in Figure 17, we create a switch congestion and activate the MAS agent to suggest the recovery procedure. We start with steady state conditions (step 1). Then, we start the traffic generator with a flow traversing N1 and N2. Congestion occurs at N1 (step 2). The MAS agent detects SLA violations in the packet-optical segment and suggests a rerouting of the application flow through possible alternative routes, i.e., through N5 or through the optical bypass (step 3). The underlying SDN controller enforces this flow rule to N1, traffic is diverted (step 4). End-to-end latency is reduced due to both the shortest hop and congestion avoidance (step 5). In this way, the SLA is fully recovered. The tests and results are reported in Section 8.

In workflow 2, shown in Figure 18, we induce latency increase at the RAN CU and enable the MAS to trigger the re-optimization. The same steady state conditions are configured (step 1). Then, we configure

an extra delay on the interface between the CU and the CN VMs (step 2). As a result, we detected RAN latency increases. The MAS agents detect SLA violation in the RAN segment and suggest drastically reducing the latency in the packet-optical domain (see tests and results in the next sections). Only the optical bypass is able to meet these new requirements, thus the MAS suggests steering to the optical bypass (step 3). The underlying SDN controller enforces this flow rule to N1 (step 4), traffic is diverted to the bypass and the SLA is recovered even in presence of an extra delay at the CU (step 5).

FIGURE 17. DEMO 1: WORKFLOW 1

FIGURE 18. DEMO 1: WORKFLOW 2

5.2. Description of Real-time Digital Twin Demonstrators

5.2.1. Introduction, Testbed and Components

This section describes the preliminary demonstrator (year 2 development release) of the Real-time Digital Twin application, also referred to as Demo 2 Y2. Hosted at the 5TONIC testbed, this demonstrator is the result of a collaborative effort among multiple partners. It implements an initial version of the distributed DT application, which was initially described as a general use case in D2.1 [15] and targeted for demonstration in D5.1 [1]. The DESIRE6G components integrated and utilized in the demo include: the DT application, entirely developed in WP5, the Service Orchestrator (SO), the Data Lake (DL), and the Service Catalogue (SC) from the SMO, the Local Network Function Virtualization Orchestrator (Local NFVO), the NF Routing (NFR), and the UE2Service Mapper from the IML, and the Per Packet Value Traffic Manager (PPV-TM). The complete description of the testbed, along with the software versions, is fully described in Section 2.1. The list of the software components developed as part of the project and integrated in the demo is reported in the table below:

TABLE 8. INTEGRATED COMPONENTS IN DEMO2 Y2

Integrated components (Responsible Partner)	Version (WP)	D6G component (release)
Data Lake/SMO (NUBIS)	C3.3001 (WP3)	Yes (R1)
Service Orchestrator/SMO (NUBIS)	C3.3002 (WP3)	Yes (R1)
Service Catalogue/SMO (NUBIS)	C3.3003 (WP3)	Yes (R1)
Local NFVO/IML (ELTE)	C4.1001 (WP4)	Yes (R1)
Per Packet Value Traffic Manager (ELTE)	C4.2002 (WP4)	Yes (R1)
NF Routing/IML (ELTE)	C4.3001 (WP4)	Yes (R1)
UE2Service Mapper/IML (ELTE)	C4.3002 (WP4)	Yes (R1)
DT distributed application (UC3M)	C5.1 (WP5)	No (R1)

- 1) In this demonstrator, we evaluate the performance of a complete end-to-end DT system distributed across the Device-Edge-Cloud continuum over a 6G network. In this setup, a quadruped robot is remotely controlled in real-time and operates executing algorithms running at the edge of the network. The robot continuously sends sensor data upstream to update its virtual model while simultaneously receiving control commands downstream. The primary challenge lies in optimizing computational, storage, and networking resources to meet the stringent KPIs required for operational digital twin use cases. To achieve this, the following components from the initial releases of WP3 and WP4 of DESIRE6G are used in this demo: **SMO**: Facilitates efficient life-cycle management automation of the DT system. Specifically, we will demonstrate:
- a. **DL**: Holds binary artifacts as container images used throughout the stack (SMO, IML).
 - b. **SC**: Contains Service Graphs for the Network Functions (NFs) and Application Functions (AFs) from the DT system to be deployed on the DESIRE6G platform.
 - c. **SO**: Receives the initial request for DT service instantiation, interacts with the SC and DL to receive the Service Graph, and forwards it to IML for service deployment.

- 2) **IML**: Provides runtime optimizations by managing the traffic load in the data plane through the benefits of network programmability, including:
 - a. **Local NFVO**: Provides NF and AF deployment on top of the K8S infrastructure and configures network function data planes to hardware data plane targets, such as Intel Tofino.
 - b. **NFR**: Processes DESIRE6G headers and implements the forwarding graph among NFs of the DT service.
 - c. **UE2Service Mapper**: Maps traffic from the robot UE to the DT service and processing DESIRE6G site.
- 3) **PPV-TM**: Tags packets from the DT service with importance values and uses an active queue management (AQM) algorithm based on queue state and packet tags to guarantee the TM policy profile.

5.2.2. Goal of the Demonstrator

The demonstration has two primary objectives:

- To showcase the D6G platform capabilities in automating the deployment of a real-time end-to-end DT system, with a focus on the integration and validation of the SMO and the IML components.
- To demonstrate programmatic traffic management of the DT system during network congestion, where the IML prioritizes essential and time sensitive robot traffic flows (i.e., LiDAR, odometry, control commands) to ensure uninterrupted and reliable system operation.

5.2.3. Demonstration Startup and Workflows

The demo starts by showcasing the deployment of the end-to-end DT service by the SMO at the D6G edge site, ensuring seamless integration and communication among the integrated D6G components.

The deployment process includes the following steps:

1. The SO receives a deployment request from the user, which specifies the service graph name and the DESIRE6G site ID. Details of the API endpoint for service deployment are provided in Figure 19.

2. The SO retrieves the service graph, structured as a YAML file, from the catalogue and forwards it to the IML for deployment. The structure of the service graph is detailed in Figure 20.
3. The IML deploys the service across the edge server and the robot, enabling the distributed DT application to operate as intended. Figure 21 highlights the key features of the implemented DT application.

```
SMO
desire6g@smo:~/unitree-go1-digital-twin/utils/d6g-demo$ curl -X POST \
-H "Content-Type: application/json" \
-d '{"json_data": {"type": "service_graph", "name": "demo_nsd.sg.yml", "site_id": "desire6g-site"}}' \
http://localhost:32008/main_id/ | jq
% Total    % Received % Xferd  Average Speed   Time    Time     Time  Current
           Dload  Upload   Total     Spent    Left     Speed
100    228    100    133    100     95      67    47    0:00:02  0:00:01  0:00:01  114
{
  "message": "Received",
  "status": "deployed",
  "service_name": "Digital Twin Demo",
  "file_name": "demo_nsd.sg.yml",
  "site_id": "desire6g-site"
}
```

FIGURE 19. DEMO 2 Y2: API ENDPOINT FOR DT SERVICE DEPLOYMENT VIA SO

```

1  lnsd: # refers to a network service graph whose subgraph is described
2  ns-instance-id: "11223344-e2a8-4338-bc8c-be685548bad2"
3  ns:
4  name: "Digital Twin Demo"
5  id: "418420e3-e2a8-4338-bc8c-be685548bad2" # refers to the ns in the service catalog
6  vendor: "D6G"
7  site-id: "d6g-001"
8
9  network-functions:
10 - nf-instance-id: "flowcl-i01" # Flow Classifier
11   nf-id: "flowcl"
12 - nf-instance-id: "firewall-i01" # ACL Firewall
13   nf-id: "firewall"
14 - nf-instance-id: "nat-i01" # NAT
15   nf-id: "nat"
16 - nf-instance-id: "dpi-i01" # DPI Middlebox
17   nf-id: "dpi"
18
19  application-functions:
20 - af-instance-id: "dt-ros-master" # ROS Master
21   af-id: "ros-master"
22 - af-instance-id: "dt-digital-replica" # Digital Twin App
23   af-id: "digital-replica"
24 - af-instance-id: "dt-gesture-control" # Gesture Control App
25   af-id: "gesture-control"
26 - af-instance-id: "dt-go1-navigation" # Go1 Navigation/SLAM
27   af-id: "go1-navigation"
28 - af-instance-id: "dt-go1-base" # Go1 Base
29   af-id: "go1-base"
30 - af-instance-id: "dt-lidar-drivers" # LiDAR Drivers
31   af-id: "lidar-drivers"
32 - af-instance-id: "dt-camera-drivers" # Camera Drivers
33   af-id: "camera-drivers"
34
35  forwarding_graphs:
36 - member-graph-index: 1 # list of subgraphs/forwarding segments implemented by the given D6G site
37   graph-name: "uplink"
38   links:
39   - id: "towebsserver"
40     connection-points:
41     - member-connection-point-index: 1
42       member-if-id-ref: "flowcl-i01:port-2"
43     - member-connection-point-index: 2
44       member-if-id-ref: "lws-i01:eth0"
45   - id: "toFW"
46     connection-points:
47     - member-connection-point-index: 1
48       member-if-id-ref: "flowcl:port-3"
49     - member-connection-point-index: 2
50       member-if-id-ref: "firewall-i01:port-1"
51 e2e_delay_budget: "10ms"

```

Service Graph
(demo_nsd.sg.yml)

FIGURE 20. DEMO 2 Y2: DT SERVICE GRAPH STRUCTURE

FIGURE 21. DEMO 2 Y2: KEY FUNCTIONALITIES OF THE DT APPLICATION

Once the service is active, the performance of the DT system is evaluated under normal operational conditions in terms of latency, jitter, and bandwidth, to establish a benchmark for future tests. Traffic monitoring is conducted using a combination of the ROS message traffic analyzer (i.e., rostopic CLI) [16] and tcpdump [17] tools.

It is important to note that the software used for communication between modules of the distributed DT application is ROS. A ROS-based system consists of software processes known as nodes that perform specific tasks (i.e., controlling movement or reporting sensor data) and communicate by exchanging structured messages through dedicated channels called topics. The transport layer of these messages relies on the TCP-based ROS Communication Protocol (TCPROS) [18] protocol, which uses standard TCP/IP sockets. Therefore, system performance was assessed by monitoring the messages exchanged between ROS nodes on the edge server and the robot via key ROS topics in the DT application. Table 9 summarizes these topics, along with their associated nodes, message types, and descriptions.

TABLE 9. DEMO 2 Y2: MONITORED ROS TOPICS FOR ROBOT-DT COMMUNICATION

Publisher node	Subscriber node	Topic	Message type	Description
Robot	Edge	/scan	sensor_msgs/LaserScan	Laser scanner distance data for SLAM
Robot	Edge	/odom	nav_msgs/Odometry	Robot position and orientation data for SLAM and DT synchronization
Robot	Edge	/joint_states	sensor_msgs/JointState	Robot joint position, velocity, and effort data for DT synchronization
Edge	Robot	/cmd_vel	geometry_msgs/Twist	High-level velocity commands for robot control

Industrial traffic is then simulated using a traffic generator server that emulates over 100 users. This simulation introduces network congestion, resulting in noticeable degraded application performance. In response, the IML activates the traffic management functionality on the programmable switch to protect the important robot traffic flows (see Figure 22). Different quality-of-service (QoS) policies are applied to ensure performance isolation among services and users, with higher bandwidth allocated to the critical traffic in the DT service. As a result, the robot continues to function effectively, even under heavy background traffic from simulated users.

FIGURE 22. DEMO 2: DT SERVICE TRAFFIC MANAGEMENT IN A CONGESTED NETWORK SCENARIO

Finally, the performance of the DT system is evaluated under network congestion by analysing key metrics. The evaluation compares the baseline PoC implementation – without D6G components – against the enhanced performance achieved with the D6G solution that incorporates traffic management features. A detailed analysis of all the tests and results can be found in Section 8.

5.3. Proof-of-Concepts (POCs)

Besides the two main demos related to the AR and DT use cases, a total of seven proof-of-concepts have been designed and realized by DESIRE6G partners. The scope of such PoCs is to integrate few specific components of Release 1 and provide an assessment of specific aspects of the DESIRE6G architecture evaluated in different use cases, testbeds and network scenarios. The deployment of proof-of-concepts is essential to provide further evidence of the benefits of specific components of the D6G architecture, that could not be highlighted adequately in the two main integrated demos. Moreover, they can provide multiple feedback to the technical Work Packages to

refine the design and the implementation of Release 2 components, following a continuous integration approach. A total of seven PoC have been designed, described in detail in the following subsections.

5.3.1. Intelligent Image Monitoring

We report the description of the preliminary experimental setup of the intelligent monitoring proof-of-concept demonstrator. This PoC demonstrates the benefits of UE-side data plane programmability, showing how it can reduce the load on wireless channels as well as the server where the stream processing is performed. The PoC is hosted in ELTE's local testbed. The experimental setup is depicted in Figure 23.

FIGURE 23. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP OF INTELLIGENT IMAGE MONITORING

The system consists of several components: 1) a video camera stream emulator server that send 4 IP camera streams to the Cloud controller. 2) a robot emulator server that generates status messages of the emulated robot at a predefined frequency (125Hz). The emulated robot follows a predefined trajectory in an emulated industrial area covered by the 4 IP cameras, as shown in Figure 24. 3) a p4-programmable GbE switch based on PCEngines APU hardware with P4-eBPF backend using NIKSS as control plane software. This node executes the robot-state-based camera stream filtering method implemented as a P4 program. The node also offers a simple REST-based stream shaping network exposure API through which robot operators can define rules that describe the importance of camera

streams at each robot states (i.e., the position in the industrial area can determine which streams are needed at good quality). 4) an industrial controller server that captures the stream and the robot states and evaluates if the required stream quality was provided by the system. This node also loads the monitoring data to influxDB can be visualized on a Grafana dashboard. The emulated wireless link is between the P4-switch and the cloud-based industrial controller.

FIGURE 24. ROBOT TRAJECTORY IN THE INDUSTRIAL AREA COVERED BY FOUR IP CAMERAS

5.3.1.1. Intelligent Image Monitoring - Test and Results

Initial evaluation results are demonstrated in the work done in In-Network Quality Control of IP Camera Streams, 6G-PDN Workshop [19]. The results show that the method can significantly reduce traffic load on the wireless channel without affecting the quality of industrial control process. In stage one the application deployment and P4 code deployment on the APU hardware was done manually.

FIGURE 25. THE METHOD HELPS TO MEET THE THROUGHPUT BUDGET ON THE CRITICAL LINK

Figure 25 depicts the traffic patterns observed during a longer time interval. The interval is split to phases labelled with corresponding setpoints of the robot (1-4) as shown in Figure 24 we can observe that streams, classified as important for the industrial process, are transmitted at high quality resulting in their original throughput demand without encountering any loss. On the other hand, unimportant streams have a load close to zero and experience high losses. However, these losses are intentional losses without causing any harm to the control functionality. Unimportant camera streams still have a non-zero throughput since I-frames need to be forwarded to keep alive the connection. We can also observe in the figure that the throughput demand of each stream smoothly follows the transitions between states determined by the robot location. Here we show that if we have two important streams at a time, the aggregated traffic fits well into the maximal 24 Mbps bottleneck capacity thus avoiding unintended loss. As a result, the important streams have perfect quality and due to the retained I-frames, we still deliver infrequently changing images for the unimportant streams, not breaking the connections of video streams.

The work on integrating the core components of the PoC with IML and SMO has already started. The intended setup is depicted in Figure 26. The network service will be deployed on two DESIRE6G sites:

- 1) a micro-site in the industrial area with a P4-programmable gateway. This gateway will be the only resource to be controlled by a local IML instance.
- 2) A larger Desire6G site with a local Kubernetes cluster and a Tofino switch used as gateway running the infrastructure network functions.

The deployment of the industrial controller and the service configuration will be managed by the site-local IML instance. IML instances will get the service graph partitions from SMO in YAML format as defined in D2.2 [20]. The data-control plane interactions will be done through the IML's control plane proxy. The stream shaping network exposure API will be available for a management node also in the network service (running at the industrial site).

FIGURE 26. ARCHITECTURE OF IMAGE MONITORING POC AFTER THE INTEGRATION WITH IML AND SMO

The network service implementing this PoC is simple containing a QoSControl network function (P4 program) and an Industrial Controller AF. In Figure 27 the traffic flows (yellow arrows) for both upstream and downstream direction along the different infrastructure network functions (UE2S - UE2Service Mapping, NFR - NF Routing) and custom network and application functions are depicted. Note that the NFR instances after at site borders acts as tunnels end-points, implementing the transport adapter function as described in D4.2 [21]. Both robot traffic and camera streams are emulated by two traffic generator servers (the streams are real-time messaging control (RTMP) flows with H265 encoding).

FIGURE 27. THE TRAFFIC FLOW ACROSS DIFFERENT NETWORK FUNCTIONS

5.3.2. ML Assisted RIS Configuration Based on FL

This PoC pertains to the hardware integration of algorithmic developments documented in Section 5.1 of D3.1 [11], for training a neural network models based on federated learning that predicts the configuration of the phase elements of reflecting intelligent surfaces (RISs). The integration is conducted in four phases, as outlined in Section 5.3.1 of D3.2 [22]. We report in the rest of this section, the final hardware integration setup (i.e., Phase 4) that comprises equipment distributed across geographically separated locations, rather than being co-located at a single site.

FIGURE 28.. OVERVIEW OF FEDERATED LEARNING ARCHITECTURE INTEGRATION WITH 5TONIC (PHASE 4)

5.3.2.1. ML Assisted RIS Configuration - Experimental Setup

Figure 28 depicts the experimental setup for the integration of underlying federated learning architecture. Note that the PoC is hosted on the 5TONIC testbed and local computers at the University of Oulu (UOU). We refer to the computers at UOU as *local* clients and those in 5TONIC as *non-local* clients. Note that the parameter server (PS) is also non-local. Each client has its own dataset corresponding to its environment; see Section 7.7. The communication between the clients and the parameter server, during the model training stage, is established using WebSocket protocols, enabling full-duplex, low-latency, and reliable data exchange over a single TCP connection.

5.3.2.2. ML Assisted RIS Configuration - Tests and Results

The ML models are trained using the experimental hardware setup discussed above. The evolution of test accuracy and training loss for the algorithms (proposed and Vanilla FL) is depicted in Figure 29. The characteristics and the benefit of proposed algorithm is discussed in D3.1 [11], and thus are extraneous to the main focus of this deliverable. However, it is important to highlight that the results obtained from the decentralized hardware setup align closely with those from the computer simulation platforms. This consistency between simulated and hardware-based results underscores the robustness and

practicality of the proposed methodologies, demonstrating their seamless transition from theoretical design and simulation to real-world implementation.

5.3.2.3. Insights into the Deployment

In a practical deployment, local and non-local clients can be considered as geo-distributed DESIRE6G sites with RISs and RIS controllers. The parameter serve can be a VM or any container within the network. In such a setting, the copies of the trained neural networks, including the global and respective local representations (see D3.1 [11]) are to be stored for instance at each RIS. The inferences in the deployment phase includes the following stages:

- **Channel Estimation:** Transmitter (Tx) and receiver (Rx) estimate the channels Tx-RIS and RIS-Rx, respectively. Then the channel state information (CSI) is sent to the RIS controller via backhaul or dedicated signalling.
- **Neural Network Computation:** The RIS controller processes the CSI as input to its NN and calculates the optimal RIS configuration.
- **RIS Configuration Update:** The RIS controller sends the computed configuration to the RIS hardware to adjust its elements.
- **Communication Optimization:** The RIS reflects signals based on the updated configuration, optimizing the Tx-Rx communication.

FIGURE 29. CONVERGENCE OF ALGORITHMS: (TOP) TEST ACCURACY, (BOTTOM) TRAINING LOSS.

5.3.3. Low Overhead Runtime Integrity Verification

A separate research action is engaged by TSS to design, test and develop a low overhead runtime integrity verification mechanism. The motivation is the elaboration of always sustainable, best-efforts generation of integrity verifications during the payload execution.

One direct benefit is to obviate the agent startup latency inevitably caused by remote attestation. Typically, exemplifying a 6G high demanding use case with ultra short zero perceived latency, demo 1's remote attestation of acting MAS agent is worked out prior to execution, typically at a time of the time of setting up demo 1 components.

In contrast, attesting the agent code when it has already started its execution drops to nil the latency at startup. The negative side is that the software has already been executing before its validation comes,

thus opening a window of attack. In the following, we dub this method of remote attestation carried out at the early stage of the program execution as *Attest-after-Starting* in contrast to the classical *Attest-before-Starting scheme*. The second benefit is to confer a permanent and continuous integrity at the start, and during the full exploitation cycle of the software.

In the state-of-the-art (SoA), runtime integrity verification is uncommon because of the performance impact it generates, and our research is fixing that core cyber security issue. As the remote attestation is done during the execution of the code and consumes resources, it is important to consider technics to restrict the resource consumption absorbed by remote attestation. The novelty of our work consists in spreading over time the resource consumption induced by the hashing of the software memory footprint, setting up interruptions of a standard Hashing SHA256 at each of its partial footprint processing stages.

Our design is two-fold with two distinct schemes based on a single thread or alternatively on two separated threads into which the program on the one hand and the remote attestation on the other hands are placed. For single or two threads schemes, we implement a spread-over-time hashing measurement. In practice this consists in placing an adjustable pause time between two loop-structured hash program's loop passes. Our past measurements are completed on the two threads (while the single thread measurements are not processed yet). The core measure is related to the performance penalty on the remotely attested programs. This is done as shown in Figure 30 below.

FIGURE 30. OVERVIEW OF THE SPREAD OVER TIME HASHING PROCESS TO MEASURE INTEGRITY

Our testbed enables the measurement of the complete execution of the program. Typical cryptographic and performance hungry programs have been considered. The same programs can be analyzed with different variables (i.e., Prime (10), Prime (10 000 000)). The core variable of our spread hashing is the idle time duration as stated above. The higher the idle time, the less resource consumption and penalty is expected.

We injected a thread into the *Prime* program, which calculates n prime numbers. This thread measures integrity during execution with different pause durations. We calculate the time delay penalty by comparing the execution time of the program with the thread to that of the original program without the thread.

The tables below show the results averaged over 100 experiments for the *Prime* program calculating 1000, 100 000 and 1 000 000 prime numbers. The first line of the tables is the duration of the original program without runtime attestation and the others are the durations of the program with runtime attestation and idle time.

The table below shows how the penalty increases based on the idle time duration for Prime 1000:

TABLE 10. PRIME PROGRAM RESULTS - CALCULATION OF 1000 PRIME NUMBERS

Program and idle time	Program duration (ms)	Penalty (%)
Original program: Prime 1000	372	NA
Prime 1000 without idle time	379.2	0.01
Prime 1000 with 10 microseconds idle time	372.9	0.24
Prime 1000 with 50 microseconds idle time	373.3	0.34
Prime 1000 with 100 microsecond idle time	375.0	0.8

TABLE 11. PRIME PROGRAM RESULTS -CALCULATION OF 100000 NUMBERS

The table below shows how the penalty increases based on the idle time duration for Prime 100 000:

Program and idle time	Program duration (ms)	Penalty (%)
Original program: Prime 100 000	292773.0	NA
Prime 100 000 without idle time	301625.6	0.03

Prime 100 000 with 100 microseconds idle time	299383.7	2.25
Prime 100 000 with 0.001 second idle time	300568.9	2.66
Prime 100 000 with 0.01 second idle time	299330.0	2.23

The table below shows how the penalty increases based on the idle time duration for Prime 1 000000:

TABLE 12. PRIME PROGRAM RESULTS -CALCULATION OF 1 000 000 PRIME NUMBERS

Program and idle time	Program duration (ms)	Penalty (%)
Original program: Prime 1 000 000	9460965.0	NA
Prime 1 000 000 without idle time	9561602.04	0.01
Prime 1 000 000 with 100 microseconds idle time	9525056.8	0.6
Prime 1 000 000 with 0.001 second idle time	9515418.7	0.57
Prime 1 000 000 with 0.01 second idle time	9472267.8	0.11

5.3.3.1. Test Results

The tables above lead to our following observation: the two threads are allocated with different resources by the operating system or the processor, typically over two different processing nodes or cores on the same node. Although the three tables show un-explained higher penalties obtained for Prime (100 000) than the ones obtained for Prime (1000) and Prime (1000 000), they all reflect that the idle time has no influence on the penalty, at least as we could foresee.

As a consequence, affecting the resources of one thread does not affect linearly the resources of the other thread (i.e., before all resources of all nodes are congested). In the majority of situations, there is no replicable relationship between the resource consumption on one resource to another. Consequently, in our tests and in certain conditions, spreading the measurement over time (i.e., augmenting the idle time), processed in the second thread, does not have a positive effect on the first thread.

As revealed by ultra-short programs, an incompressible bulk (i.e., minimal penalty that cannot be lessened) is revealed, about dozens of micro-seconds. Our interpretation is that it is caused by the second thread on-the-fly generation (with memory mapping, processor register-context switch) and deviation to the second thread. This is done by a system call clone. For long lasting program, the impact of remote attestation on performance is imperceptible.

PoC's road map

- Prioritizing the two-thread scheme, viewed as offering promising exploitable results with two possible methods implemented on Demo1's agent.
 - *Attest-after-starting* method, permitting instant agent's start.
 - Attest-after-running method to drop penalty down to nil is stated

At completion of the two-thread scheme, we will jump start the mono-thread scheme, where our considered spread-over-time hashing, leveraging an interrupted-paused hashing measurement method is expected to bear fruit. The perspective of getting results in terms of measures or a

demonstrator inside this PoC will be defined once we will have progressed this research. According to our progression, the outcome may not be demonstrated in this PoC.

5.3.4. Software Performance Monitoring by Selected Code Block Trampolining Applied to L2Fwd NF

The objective of this PoC is to showcase how an uninterrupted network function L2Fwd can be performance monitored during its execution, at low resource overhead. The demonstration will first recall the problem statement and operational hurdles brought by classical profiling tools and the objectives of our solution.

The PoC will be structured over a testbed which can be a combination of TSS/ERICSSON-HU or TSS only (as existing today and for our running development). The testbed will use a traffic generation and will show how a stress on L2Fwd can be instantly detected by our technique. The demonstration will emphasize on the benefits of the solution acting at early stage and before L2Fwd drops.

FIGURE 31. GENERIC TESTBED OVER L2FWD NETWORK FUNCTION

The PoC demonstration will be structured over three novel KPIs of Confidence/Convergence and Penalty or alternatively over ISO Security Usability criteria (Effectiveness, Efficiency and Satisfaction).

5.3.4.1. Software Performance Monitoring by Selected Code Block Trampoline Applied to L2Fwd NF - Test and Results

Definition of the testbed

Our testbed includes a DPDK traffic generation with L2FWD network function into two different interconnected VMs. Our testbed also integrates PCAP++ library

Separately, our testbed enables to develop and test our self-monitoring technique, consisting in placing code snippets directly in the program binary file to extract time and frequency metrics as discussed below.

Development of self-monitoring technique

Our work has consisted in placing e9patch trampolines over the code control flow (i.e., hooking jump and call instructions). E9patch enables to instrument binary files with the placement of trampolines which redirect the control flow to arbitrarily defined trampolines (i.e., for different types of assembly instructions). Our trampolines are aimed at generating timestamps before returning to the called or jumped code blocks as shown in the Figure 32. Timestamps can be placed either at or both code block entry or exit.

FIGURE 32.. REPRESENTATION OF DIFFERENT CODE BLOCK ENTRIES

Collected measurements

- The objective is to grasp as micro level (i.e., code block level) the performance deviation of the macro level (i.e., the complete program). This shall be done without inflicting a penalty induced by the monitoring itself.
- Time and frequency measures have been collected over a representative set of executables (e.g., Prime, Binserve). They are the Execution Time (ET) of a program's code block and the Call Frequency (CF) of the code block. The standard deviations of CF and ET have also been collected.
- We had to solve major discrepancies in our collected measurements, that we attributed to the control flow undecidability, where code blocks can be jump-started or left anywhere inside them. In these situations, the measurements of CF and ET are meaningless and incorrect.
- We had also measured and collected the performance penalty (i.e., percentage of performance decrease) of our self-monitoring method. Indeed, to attain other KPIs of measure accuracy and convergence (i.e., time to produce a measure), it is essential to limit the penalty to limit the penalty to an acceptable level (e.g., <1%). Conversely, if the penalty is high, self-monitoring usage will be very limited. In that sake, we have been fast to collect unsustainable penalties by e9patch trampolining if applied blindly (on all code blocks). A selective approach shall be followed.
- The code block selection as stated above came with highly diverging results from one code block to another. The table below shows the impact of the stress according to different strategies of block selection

TABLE 13. RESULTS OF A PATCHED BINARY WHEN UNDER STRESS* COMPARED TO THE SAME PATCHED BINARY RUNNING FOR THE SAME TIME IN NORMAL CONDITIONS

Code block used				
Average Block CF	x530 ↓	x32 ↓	x537 ↓	x10 ↓
Average Block ET	x600 ↑	x30 ↑	x538 ↑	x10 ↑
ET Standard Deviation	x400 ↑	x5 ↑	x43 ↑	x3 ↑

- Our observation of collected CF and ET measures revealed that CF is more accurate than ET as it reflects a performance drop outside the considered code block, hence closer to the monitored code in its whole. As a matter of a drop of CF means that all code outside the code block is getting slower (as the code block is less often called). ET reversely reflects the inner working of the selected code block; without assurance the code block is a good characterization of the whole program.
- A stressed processor, through its scheduler, interrupts the execution of all code blocks altogether. The scheduler puts on hold the process (i.e., including all code blocks). Figure 33 shows the behavior of a normal execution program and stressed execution.

FIGURE 33. . NORMAL EXECUTION PROGRAM BEHAVIOUR VS. STRESSED EXECUTION PROGRAM

To overcome the undecidability issue, two types of reference code blocks have been considered: Reference code block Execution Time (ET) and reference code block Call Frequency (CF). These reference code blocks are post-compilation inserted, closing the door to mid-way jumpstart or quit.

- With a prevalence on CF, viewed as being more accurate than ET, work has been done on CF. As shown by this curve of the average call frequency (i.e., quantity of calls in a given observation time) of the reference block as a function of the stress level, with Quadratic Interpolation (Q.I). The QI curve and the real measures are perfectly overlapping. Once generated (with the support of sufficient real measures), the Q.I curve can be used for assessing the CPU stress level at any given CF measure.

FIGURE 34.. STRESS LEVEL DEPENDING ON CALL FREQUENCY OF REFERENCE BLOCK

Current road map:

In view of the PoC and timeline, we will follow the PoC design and road map as below:

PoC selected measurement method:

- Leverage CF metric with two declinations: use it as a direct measure of the performance penalty or use it to assess the stress level over the platform.
- Elaborate a pre-deployment calibration method to collect the reference code block CF average in normal and stress conditions and generate the stress level versus CF curve as shown above.

Definition of the PoC KPIs:

We will elaborate the used KPIs to assess the performance of our self-monitoring method. These KPIs will reflect the accuracy of the measurement, the penalty induced by the self-monitoring itself, the convergence (i.e., time to make a measurement) and its usability in terms of easy use.

Coordination with ERI-HU:

The goal of our collaboration with ERI-HU is to elaborate the PoC demonstration. We will reset the initial testbed, using L2Fwd or a_X86 ELF binary compiled from a P4 code.

We will elaborate the testbed ideal for low-noise measurements, relevance of the measures produced and portability of the testbed between partners.

5.3.5. In-band Telemetry and Control

The objective of this PoC is to showcase how data plane programmability can facilitate faster control loops for network automation, by employing in-network control and monitoring of traffic flows using INT [23]. Specifically, it showcases flexible and dynamic flow steering through the network, enabled by (i) ultra-fast identification of changes in the network state (i.e., detection of incipient congestion or degradation in the trustworthiness of the flow path), and (ii) exchanging control messages through the in-network communication channel, allowing the network to react immediately and steer the traffic flows via alternative (trust- and QoS equivalent) routes, with no CPU involvement.

Since INT is enabled, all switches are instrumented to generate INT reports for all traffic, reporting per-packet metadata such as the switch ID, latency, queue congestion status, trust level and path tracing info [24]. The trust level of a switch is based on several device-specific metrics, such as physical location, running firmware, operator, and similar criteria. The trustworthiness of a path is calculated as the minimum trust of the nodes participating in the path [25]. Report generation is handled entirely at the data plane, in a way that does not affect the performance observed by regular traffic. The approach aims to significantly reduce reaction times by the infrastructure elements and improve the accuracy of the monitoring information. The structure of the Telemetry Headers is depicted in Figure 35. Telemetry data such as the path tracing and trust related information is embedded to the packet as TCP Options, while an additional header is added conveying congestion related metadata.

FIGURE 35. TELEMETRY HEADER

The PoC is hosted in the ARNO testbed. The experimental setup is depicted in Figure 36.

FIGURE 36. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP OF IN-BAND TELEMETRY AND CONTROL

The system consists of the following components:

1. P4-programmable switches that support PLINT and standard INT. The programmable switches are running the Nikss software, providing an efficient implementation of fully configurable P4 switches, able to transmit the packets at wire speed. The switches run on general-purpose CPUs. Therefore, each switch operates on a dedicated server to achieve maximum efficiency. The optical bypass is facilitated by a commercial packet router and a pair of OTN optical transport

ROADMs, which include muxponder cards operating at 100G with coherent DSP and 10Gb/s Ethernet tributaries.

2. The telemetry collector, a P4-programmable switch, performs in-network aggregation at wire speed, and is responsible for the collection, aggregation, filtering, and correlation of the data. In essence it facilitates (i) the real-time identification of bottlenecks or unsolicited changes in the trust level of the flow path and (ii) real-time or near real-time control loops, utilizing predefined control policies installed in the switch, or by feeding information to the network controller, which dynamically makes decisions for near real-time closed loop operations. In this PoC, we showcase the former.
3. The telemetry information is being forwarded from the collector switch to a telemetry server embedded into layer 2 data packets. The monitoring data are stored in an influxDB can be visualized on a Grafana dashboard. Specifically, a visualization of the topology graph and the state of the data flows is provided in real-time, as well as congestion and trust (per path) related information.
4. Traffic is generated with a Spirent N4U traffic generator/analyser, with a pair of Ethernet interfaces at 10GB/s, injecting and receiving traffic with specific characteristics.

In stage 1 we evaluate the Efficiency of the proposed approach on the (fast) identification of QoS or trust related service degradation, and the use of an in-network control channel to implement corrective measures for service assurance [26] for example, INT allows the early detection of bottlenecks or unsolicited changes in the trust level of the data flow path (B3-P41-P42) at the telemetry collector. Consequently, the collector will request network service adaptation using predefined control policies installed at both the collector and the network switches. This is achieved through sending the INT-triggered control message with a steering flag ON in the reverse path, prompting the use of the optical bypass path (B3-O1-O2-P42), which is the pre-defined backup path that adheres to the QoS and Trust requirements of the flow. Stage 2 will involve alignment of the proposed solution with D6G service monitoring, in terms of i.e., the INT and control header structure, interfacing the telemetry collector with the respecting telemetry agent to support the near-real time control loop etc. Advancements in that direction will be reported in D4.2 and further integrated deployment of components will be reported in D5.3 .

5.3.5.1 In-band Telemetry and Control - Test and Results

To cover Stage 1, we introduce background traffic in the packet router that will eventually lead to congestion in the data path. Specifically, we are causing congestion by sending multiple flows of 130 Mbps at P42.

Main Path P4 Switches

Switch Packet Queue Length

A

B

FIGURE 37. INT DASHBOARD INDICATING CHANGE OF PATH DUE TO CONGESTION.

Initially, the Dashboard shows an increase in queue length at switch P41, as can be seen in Figure 37a, indicating a bottleneck. Congestion detection is based on predefined thresholds for metrics such as queue size or delay, which serve as indicators of a potential SLA violation. When congestion is detected by the *Telemetry Collector*, it triggers a network service adaptation request. This process is executed by sending an INT-triggered control message with the Steering Flag set to ON in the reverse path, activating the optical bypass switches O1 and O2. This backup path is pre-defined to meet the QoS and Trust requirements of the flow. The new path is then visible on the Dashboard, where the active path's colour updates accordingly as shown in Figure 37, notifying the operator of the new active path and confirming that it adheres to the required QoS and Trust policies.

5.3.6 PREOF

PREOF-DetNet is responsible for establishing a deterministic transport network connecting DESIRE6G sites, enhancing network reliability. Figure 38 illustrates PREOF-DetNet within the DESIRE6G.

FIGURE 38. PREOF-DETNET IN DESIRE6G

This scenario consists of a traffic generator and four blocks representing a deterministic domain with PREOF. These blocks are: PRF, SWAP-MPLS, PEF, and POF. See Figure 38.

This system operates as follows during runtime:

1. The Traffic Generator produces IP traffic and sends it to the PRF block.
2. The PRF block converts the IP packet into a DetNet packet by adding the necessary headers (Control Word, S-Label, and MPLS) and duplicates the packets to send them through all possible paths to the destination.
3. If the packets reach the SWAP-MPLS block, the appropriate fields are modified to forward the packet to the destination. If they reach the PEF block, it will maintain a history of the packets passing through this block and discard duplicates based on this history. It will also forward the packets to the destination.
4. Out-of-order packets that arrive at the POF block are reordered and converted back into IP packets by removing the DetNet-specific headers.
5. Finally, the Traffic Generator will receive IP packets.

FIGURE 39. LOGICAL PREOF-DETNET SCENARIO

5.3.6.1 PREOF - Test and Results

Initially, to conduct tests on this equipment and improve the algorithm, the Scapy traffic generator was used, and installed on a virtual machine within the server. For example, it was employed for early tests with the Tofino switches or to send unordered packets directly to the DPDK server and observe how they were reordered. Subsequently, in this setup, the server was replaced with a realistic traffic generator typically used in network field operations—Spirent. Using Spirent, we identified implementation errors in the algorithm developed for the Tofino switches, as the system could not function correctly at high speeds. Ultimately, the issue was resolved, and it was verified that the component developed with the Tofino switches operates with traffic up to 10G. However, due to the limitations of the DPDK card we are using, it has been verified that the ordering component functions with traffic up to 1G.

As ongoing work, tests are planned with the IXIA-NE2 disturbance equipment, such as unordered fluid traffic.

5.3.7 Lightweight Virtualization Sandboxing for Cloud Native Workloads

The DESIRE6G project aims, among others, to enhance the efficiency, security, and scalability of cloud-native workloads through lightweight virtualization techniques. One of the key technologies leveraged in this direction is Kata Containers, an open-source project that offers a secure and efficient runtime environment for containerized applications. This proof of concept showcases the integration of Kata Containers into the DESIRE6G architecture to address the project's requirements for performance and security.

The main objective is to demonstrate how lightweight virtualization can be effectively utilized within the DESIRE6G framework to meet the demands of next generation 6G networks. Kata Containers leverage hardware virtualization technologies to offer robust separation between containers while maintaining performance efficiency. This is achieved by launching containers within micro VMs managed by hypervisors, each with its own kernel and root file system, thereby enhancing security and isolation, see Figure 40. This setup protects applications from remote execution, memory leaks, unprivileged access, and safeguards the host system from untrusted or untested programs. The use of Kata Containers aligns with DESIRE6G's goals by providing enhanced security through hardware

virtualization and offering robust isolation between containers, maintaining the security integrity of applications running on shared infrastructure.

FIGURE 40. TRADITIONAL VS SANDBOXED CONTAINERS PARADIGM

Figure 41 presents the interaction of the kata-containers runtime with high-level orchestrators such as k8s, through high-level container runtimes such as containerd. In DESIRE6G we follow this approach and deploy sandboxed containers throughout the whole continuum (SMO, IML).

FIGURE 41. CONTAINER RUNTIME DESIGN

In the DESIRE6G project, the deployment of a simple web server workload serves as the primary demonstrator for this proof of concept. This workload is tested in three configurations: traditional container using a standard container runtime, sandboxed container utilizing Kata Containers over hypervisors such as QEMU, Cloud Hypervisor, Firecracker, or Dragonball, and unikernel using urunc for optimized lightweight VMs. Network and application functions are packaged as OCI artifacts and

deployed in multiple formats, ensuring compatibility and flexibility in deployment strategies. This setup is designed to showcase the secure and efficient handling of cloud-native workloads in a 6G context.

FIGURE 42. APPLICATION DEPLOYMENT WORKFLOW

This framework provides secure, efficient, and scalable deployment of applications in modern cloud environments, exemplifying the DESIRE6G project’s commitment to leveraging cutting-edge technologies for enhanced security and performance in cloud-native workloads (Figure 42).

The runtime is compatible with containerd runtime shimv2 architecture and complies with the Open Container Initiative (OCI) runtime specification, making it Kubernetes-compatible with either CRI-O or the equivalent containerd implementation. A single runtime shim is sufficient to manage all OCI containers of an entire pod. Kata utilizes its agent, a daemon process, to establish robust communication between the guest and the host through a vsock socket operating on a ttRPC-based protocol. This approach enables the exchange of container management commands and standard I/O streams between a container and its manager, eliminating the need for multiple runtime calls. Such a structure ensures that Kata remains agnostic to sandbox mechanisms, allowing a plethora of different hypervisors and different types of containers such as WebAssembly (Wasm) or Linux, not just virtualized ones, suiting different demands and preferences.

The integration of Kata Containers into the DESIRE6G platform involves several components developed in other work packages (WP3 and WP4). The Service Orchestrator (SO) manages the lifecycle of services

and ensures that containerized workloads are deployed and scaled efficiently across the DESIRE6G infrastructure. The Data Lake (DL) stores binary artifacts as container images, facilitating the deployment and management of containerized applications. The Local Network Function Virtualization Orchestrator (Local NFVO) deploys network functions on Kubernetes infrastructure and configures the data plane, ensuring optimal performance and resource utilization. The Telemetry Agent and Collector provide real-time monitoring and analytics to ensure that the performance metrics of the containerized workloads meet the required KPIs.

5.3.7.1. Lightweight Virtualization Sandboxing for Cloud Native Workloads - Test and Results

TABLE 14. WEB-SERVER WORKLOAD

	Generic Container	Sandboxed Containers (software)	Sandboxed containers (hardware)	Unikernels
CPU	1.00	1.44	1.70	0.42
MEM	1.00	1.07	1.66	0.66
STORAGE	1.00	1.24	2.79	0.27

Tables 14 and 15 illustrate the overhead of each approach for running a simple web server workload (nginx) and a key-value store workload (redis). Across all modes of execution, including generic containers, software sandboxed containers, hardware sandboxed containers, and unikernels, the CPU throughput, actual memory footprint (RSS), and offline storage footprint are measured relative to the baseline of running the applications in generic containers.

TABLE 15. KEY-VALUE STORE WORKLOAD

	Generic Container	Sandboxed Containers (software)	Sandboxed containers (hardware)	Unikernels
CPU	1	2.03	1.02	0.91
MEM	1	1.39	1.71	0.65
STORAGE	1	1.22	2.64	0.21

For the web-server workload example (nginx), we can derive the following observations:

- Generic Containers: Baseline performance.
- Software Sandboxed Containers: Shows increased CPU and memory overhead compared to Generic Containers, indicating the additional resources required for software-based isolation.
- Hardware Sandboxed Containers: Demonstrates even higher CPU, memory, and storage overhead, reflecting the cost of hardware-based isolation mechanisms.
- Unikernels: Exhibits significantly reduced CPU, memory, and storage footprints compared to other execution modes, highlighting the efficiency gains of unikernels.

For the key-value store example (redis), similar trends are observed across all execution modes, with varying degrees of overhead in CPU, memory, and storage footprint. Unikernels consistently show the lowest resource overhead, making them an attractive option for running Redis and similar workloads.

5.3.8. Deployment of Secure Machine Learning Pipelines for Near-Real-Time Control of 6G Network Services

This demonstration has shown a complete solution integrating several components, including (i) the Machine Learning Function Orchestrator (MLFO) that coordinates the optimal deployment of agents and their configuration, with the help of a Service Management and Orchestration System (SMO) and an Infrastructure Management Layer (IML); (ii) a SECaaS automatic executable rewriting tool, that creates hardened, authenticable and self-monitored agents; and (iii) a DLT, combining blockchain and smart contracts. A key aspect is the showcase of agents being dynamically associated to the DLT to exchange keys and mutual attestation records through specifically designed smart contracts deployed for the Network Service (NS).

FIGURE 43. DESIRE6G ARCHITECTURE FOR SECURE DISTRIBUTED INTELLIGENCE

Figure 43 shows an overview of the essential DESIRE6G components required for executing the secure distributed intelligence. The architecture comprises multiple D6G sites in different geographical

locations, each equipped with local networking, computing, and storage resources. Central to this architecture is the D6G SMO layer, which is in charge of the orchestration and lifecycle management aspects of the NS, providing guidelines for the agents and enabling them to operate autonomously. Within the SMO, an MLFO determines the deployment locations and connections of agents. A SECaaS tool is used to improve the security of the agents by adding distributed attestation sub-routines for measurement and verification to their software. The Service Orchestrator (SO) is the responsible component in the SMO to coordinate the deployment, where the IML is in charge of the interactions with the local virtual infrastructure.

Finally, a blockchain infrastructure is also part of the D6G solution that sets up two distinct smart contracts. The first contract dynamically manages the measurement and verification functions of agents, enabling mutual remote attestation mechanisms between agents. This allows each agent to check the integrity of another agent in the system, avoiding a centralized, Deny-of-Service-vulnerable verifier. The second contract ensures a secure exchange of keys/secrets for inter-agent communications. It is worth mentioning that the DESIRE6G architecture offers a multi-use case blockchain framework, which, besides securing the MAS, also supports a federation of services.

FIGURE 44. MAS PIPELINE DEPLOYMENT WITH INITIAL MUTUAL ATTESTATION

Figure 44 outlines the proposed workflow for the MAS Pipeline deployment, which includes the MAS agents, their initial mutual attestation process, and their connectivity. This workflow consists of four phases: (i) deployment of the MAS pipeline; (ii) configuration of protected agents through a SECaaS binary hardening tool; (iii) mutual attestation; and (iv) secret/key exchange. The workflow is initiated by the SO during the deployment of the NS (step 0 in Figure 44).

The SO starts with deploying the MAS pipeline and requests the computation of the topology of a MAS pipeline given the relevant details of the NS, i.e., the location of the VNFs, the performance required for that service, etc. (1). The MLFO computes the optimal MAS pipeline and returns a descriptor that specifies the agents’ deployment location, booting image, and connectivity. The SO then interacts with the IML

components at different D6G sites to deploy each agent (2). Inter-agent connectivity based on a VXLAN that connects the D6G sites is also deployed in this step (not shown in Figure 44).

Once the agents are running and connectivity is established, the configuration of the agents starts (3). In this phase, the SECaaS system processes the native agent software (i.e., x86) and improves its security properties by including measurement, verification, and communication subroutines. Through this *wrapping* technique, SECaaS generates a reference measurement of the agent and stores it in a secure repository, ensuring its integrity for future verifications (4). Figure 45 shows the request sent to the SECaaS to wrap each agent's binary.

Source	Destination	Protocol	Info
OSM	MLFO	HTTP	POST /mlfo?command=new_service HTTP/1.1
MLFO	OSM	HTTP/JSON	HTTP/1.1 200 OK , JSON (application/json)
MLFO	OSM	TLSv1.2	Application Data
MLFO	OSM	TLSv1.2	Application Data
OSM	MLFO	TLSv1.2	Application Data
OSM	MLFO	TLSv1.2	Application Data
MLFO	SECaaS	HTTP	POST /wrap HTTP/1.1
SECaaS	MLFO	HTTP/JSON	HTTP/1.1 200 OK , JSON (application/json)
MLFO	SECaaS	HTTP	POST /wrap HTTP/1.1
SECaaS	MLFO	HTTP/JSON	HTTP/1.1 200 OK , JSON (application/json)
MLFO	SECaaS	HTTP	POST /wrap HTTP/1.1
SECaaS	MLFO	HTTP/JSON	HTTP/1.1 200 OK , JSON (application/json)
MLFO	DLT	TLSv1.2	Application Data
MLFO	DLT	TLSv1.2	Application Data
DLT	MLFO	TLSv1.2	Application Data
MLFO	Agent-1	HTTP/JSON	POST /dlt?command=set_credentials HTTP/1.1 , JSON (application/json)
Agent-1	MLFO	HTTP/JSON	HTTP/1.1 200 OK , JSON (application/json)
MLFO	Agent-2	HTTP/JSON	POST /dlt?command=set_credentials HTTP/1.1 , JSON (application/json)
Agent-2	MLFO	HTTP/JSON	HTTP/1.1 200 OK , JSON (application/json)

```

Frame 1021: 52144 bytes on wire (417152 bits), 52144 bytes captured (417152 bits) on interface unknown, id 0
Ethernet II, Src: fa:16:3e:ce:72:15, Dst: fa:16:3e:ea:7f:9c
Internet Protocol Version 4, Src: MLFO (192.168.30.228), Dst: SECaaS (192.168.30.112)
Transmission Control Protocol, Src Port: 52390, Dst Port: 8001, Seq: 48719788, Ack: 1, Len: 52078
[1014 Reassembled TCP Segments (48771865 bytes): #8(259), #9(7240), #10(5792), #11(2896), #12(11584), #13(8688)]
Hypertext Transfer Protocol
MIME Multipart Media Encapsulation, Type: multipart/form-data, Boundary: "70e8126e7691f7272ec01c12edf8c775"

```

FIGURE 45. WRAPPING REQUEST

The MLFO then deploys the wrapped images of the agents in the sites (5). Next, it creates smart contracts that will be used to record the state of agents during the remote attestation workflow and store the secrets/keys for the MAS pipeline (6). It also creates blockchain accounts for the agents, including a public address and private key, deploys smart contracts to the blockchain network, and registers the agents' addresses (7). This allows the MLFO to control access to the smart contracts and add or revoke permissions in case of MAS pipeline reconfiguration or detection of infected agents. Once the addresses are registered, the MLFO distributes the blockchain credentials to the agents involved in the MAS

pipeline for interaction with the smart contracts (8). Figure 46 shows the request send to the MAS agents including the blockchain credentials.

FIGURE 46. SET AGENT'S CREDENTIALS REQUEST

To face group attacks, where a corrupted agent verifies another corrupted agent, an initial *root of trust* (RoT) is established for the first agent verification. To that end, the first attestation is triggered by the SECaaS when the MLFO confirms that the MAS configuration has finished (9). For the initial attestation, SECaaS prepares a remote attestation plan and asks the agents to run their attestation sub-routines for measurement and verification (10). The resulting hash value from the measurements (11) is compared to the one stored in the SECaaS repository and if it matches the agent is verified. A transaction is created in the blockchain for each remote attestation, including the test result, the identifiers of the involved agents (i.e., measured and verifier ID), a timestamp, and the updated RoT (i.e., last verified agent) in the first smart contract (12).

Figure 47 shows the web user interface used to demonstrate the mutual remote attestation process in a graphical way. SeCaaS starts the process by verifying the first agent and generates a measurement, then it moves the responsibility to check the next agent to the already verified agent. Once all the agents are verified the mutual remote attestation process ends.

FIGURE 47. MULTI-STEP REMOTE ATTESTATION UI

FIGURE 48. REMOTE ATTESTATION UI

Once the NS operation phase starts, the smart contract automatically manages the remote attestation process through an internal function that receives a group attestation scheduling plan (the sequence of agents for verification) and notifies the RoT with the reference measurement of the agent, without compromising its confidentiality to other potentially infected agents. These steps are performed periodically throughout the NS lifecycle. Finally, the MLFO pushes to the second smart contract the key/secret that the agents need to use to encrypt the inter-agent communication through the VXLAN (13-14).

After successfully deploying the agents, the operation phase starts. In this demonstration, each agent sends a message to the others and traffic measurements are sent to a central entity that collects all of

them. Figure 49 shows different plots representing the total number of messages received by each agent and the traffic measurements sent by each agent to a centralized entity.

FIGURE 49. TRAFFIC MEASUREMENTS AND AGENT'S TOTAL MESSAGES

Figure 50 shows the distribution of the deployed software on the experimental testbed. This is composed by several virtual machines and OpenStack instances.

FIGURE 50. EXPERIMENTAL TESTBED

The algorithms and interfaces in the agents and the MLFO have been implemented in Python 3.10.4 and run inside Docker containers. The smart contracts have been written in the Solidity programming language. Opensource MANO (OSM) is the selected orchestration system in charge of the deployment of NSs. OpenDaylight (ODL) SDN controller is on top of the packet network and used to create the connectivity for the MAS pipeline. A scenario with three D6G locations will be showcased, where (OpenStack) is the selected IML in charge of automating the deployment of VNFs. The setup will run in several VMs deployed at the UPC premises in Barcelona Spain, with Ubuntu Server 22.04 LTS as operating system. OSM v.14 and ODL release 16.0 Sulfur will be deployed in a single VM, while three instances of OpenStack release 2023.1 Antelope manage IT resources in the locations. Finally, four container-based DLT nodes, based on the Geth implementation of the Ethereum blockchain, will also be setup.

5.3.9. MAS and Telemetry for Service Operation Demo

This demonstration has covered solutions for meeting the requirements from novel 6G services, which will require bounded delay assurance even under highly dynamic network conditions. Thus, being able to make near-real-time decisions can significantly reduce capital and operational costs for network operators. Specifically, the demonstration aims at answering questions such as whether a distributed MAS fed with INT can efficiently make near-real-time network operational decisions.

FIGURE 51. ILLUSTRATIVE EXAMPLE OF MAS AND TELEMETRY FOR SERVICE OPERATION

This demonstration aims at experimentally assessing the feasibility of a distributed MAS fed with telemetry measurements to perform near-real-time flow routing operation. For illustrative purposes, Figure 51 shows an example where several traffic flows (F_i to F_k), each following a multi-path routing strategy, enter and leave a network at different packet nodes. In the example, traffic flow F_i (from R1 to R5) can follow three different routes, where p_1 and p_2 are multi-hop paths on the packet network, whilst p_3 uses an optical bypass connecting R1 and R5 through the underlying optical network. We assume that traffic flows are *splitable*, i.e., they consist of a large number of sub-flows that can be routed independently. The objective is to find the flow routing policy that balances the incoming traffic of the flows among the available paths, so to ensure per-flow QoS (specifically e2e delay). Such routing policy varies as a function of the incoming traffic of the flow and the network conditions, i.e., the traffic of the rest of the traffic flows in the network. Therefore, the routing policy decision making process is

continuously carried out based on the incoming traffic and the e2e delay measurements that allow evaluating the quality of the decision making. Note that the state of the network is known, and it is indirectly represented by e2e delay measurements for the traffic flow. In this demonstration, we rely on the INT functionality provided by the P4 switches to measure packet delay. Specifically, a P4 collector that collects, aggregates, and provides statistics of the delay measured by the switches supporting the traffic flows has been showcased. Once the P4 collector preprocesses the QoS measurements, they are sent to a telemetry agent, which is in charge of producing flow telemetry statistics that are sent to the flow agent deployed at the source node, where flow routing policy decisions are made.

FIGURE 52. FEDERATED TESTBED SETUP FOR THE DEMONSTRATION

Figure 52 presents the federated testbed and the experimental setup to be deployed for this demonstration, which reproduces a 5-node network scenario similar to that in 55. The packet-optical network will be deployed at the CNIT/SSSA ARNO testbed, whereas the distributed MAS is deployed at UPC premises. Five native in-kernel P4-programmable software switches (P4-NIKSS) will be deployed

and connected to create the packet network. P4 switches are interconnected among them using 10G interfaces. P4 switches run on a separate server to maximize performance. Specifically, Intel(R) Xeon(R) Gold 6238R CPU @2.20GHz server with 256GB RAM are used. An additional P4-based software process is used as telemetry data collector, which receives INT data from the P4 switches. In order to reproduce network congestion and selectively introduce delay in some of the paths of the traffic flows, a Juniper M10i router equipped with 1G interfaces is connected to switch R1, as depicted in the inner graph in Figure 52. Selected flows are forced to traverse the Juniper router before route switching, thus generating different congestion scenarios. Regarding the optical layer, the optical bypass between R1 and R5 is based on a pre-programmed packet-optical Whitebox employing 10G and 100G optical pluggables. The pluggables are connected to an Optical Line System (OLS) by means of an arrayed waveguide gratings multiplexer. The OLS is composed of three 80km fiber spans and line optical amplifiers. The optical connection between the two pluggables is pre-established and enforced locally by OpenConfig-enabled SDN agents co-located with the SONiC node operating system. Finally, a Spirent SPT N4U equipped with 10G ports is used as packet generator for two different traffic flows (f_1 and f_2), both from R1 to R5. In our case, flows are identified by source and destination IP. For validation purposes, the Spirent tool is also used as flow traffic sink.

Figure 53 shows the graphical interface used to setup the flows on the Spirent SPT N4U device. In the demonstration, R1 will measure per-flow traffic entering the switch, before being forwarded through the different paths. In particular, three alternative paths are considered: p_1 (R1-R2-R5), p_2 (R1-R3-R4-R5), and p_3 (R1-R5, using the optical bypass).

FIGURE 53. SPIRENT TESTCENTER INTERFACE

The distributed system consists of several interconnected software components. Specifically, the *telemetry agent*, which is part of the distributed telemetry architecture, includes: *i*) a telemetry collector that periodically receives telemetry data from the P4 collector; and *ii*) a per-flow telemetry processor. The role of these telemetry components is to compute the required measurements and statistics that characterize the current QoS of the traffic flow, from the received INT telemetry. In addition, *flow agents* are grouped in a single module per location named *multi-flow agent*. In this case, the multi-flow agent at R1 includes flow agents for both *f1* and *f2*. Note that one single flow agent makes routing decisions for each traffic flow. The *manager* running inside multi-flow agents has the role of collecting and distributing flow telemetry data and local input traffic data to the flow agents, as well as to push the flow routing policies computed by flow agents to the P4 switch. The demonstration will rely on REST API interfaces between agents and P4 systems. MAS agents and components (including interfaces) are implemented in Python 3.10.4 and run inside Docker containers running on 2 separated VMs with Ubuntu Server 22.04 LTS as operating system.

The workflow demonstrated for traffic flows *f1* and *f2* is outlined in Figure 54. In addition, Figure 55 presents examples of some selected messages exchanged (identified with the labels in the workflow). Let us assume that flow routing policies are configured at switch R1 (0 in Figure 54) to enable multi-path

routing. Input flow traffic measurements are collected and sent periodically to the local multi-flow agent for every traffic flow entering in the network (1); the messages contain both packet and bit count for every traffic flow (see the details in Figure 54). Packet delay measured along the path is reported through INT messages to the P4 collector (2), which performs aggregations and computes statistics, i.e., min, average, and max of delay and jitter. Periodically, the P4 collector sends the computed delay statistics to the collector in the local telemetry agent (3). In addition, delay statistics are reported to a centralized telemetry system that stores them in a time series database (not shown in the workflow in Figure 54). The aggregated QoS telemetry message includes per-path statistics for every flow (Figure 55). The received statistics are then processed by each of the flow processors (4) that computes per-flow QoS telemetry measurements and send them to the corresponding flow agent (5). When flow QoS statistics are received in the multi-flow agent, the manager triggers its analysis by pushing both traffic and QoS measurements to the corresponding flow agent (6). A pre-trained reinforcement learning model makes routing decisions, with the operational objective of guaranteeing that the e2e delay does not exceed a configured threshold (QoS requirement), while minimizing the use of the optical bypass. However, to be able to interact with the system, in this demonstration, we have used a parameterized deterministic algorithm (7), so different routing policies can be manually forced by changing the values of some parameters, i.e., to force using the optical bypass. Routing decisions are gathered by the manager that eventually sends them to the P4 switch (8). The details of message 8 in Figure 55 show that a routing policy is defined as the percentages of input traffic to be routed through each of the routes. Internally, the P4 switch translates this policy into flow rules to efficiently perform packet forwarding according to defined percentages.

FIGURE 54. NEAR-REAL-TIME OPERATION WORKFLOW TO BE DEMONSTRATED

FIGURE 55. SELECTED EXCHANGED MESSAGES

Figure 56 and Figure 57 show the plots of the measured delay. In the first figure, the introduction of a new flow causes the delay to increase due to the congestion of the link. After the congestion is detected, a path reconfiguration is applied on the of the flows and the delay of the flows is mitigated.

FIGURE 56. DELAY MEASUREMENTS WITH CONGESTION

FIGURE 57. DELAY MEASUREMENTS AFTER FLOW RECONFIGURATION

6. Final Demo Execution Plan for Individual DESIRE6G Components

6.1. Demo 1 Intelligent and Resilient VR/AR Application with Perceived Zero Latency

Demo 1 will integrate all the macro-components and technologies to achieve the project's goals and assess the KPIs. This section presents the finalized execution plan for Demo 1, covering workflows, deployment strategies, and integration policies based on the latest discussions.

Demo 1 incorporates a D6G network setup integrating RAN, MAS, pervasive monitoring, IML, SecAAS and SMO. The AR application will be finalized to showcase the full chain represented by the drone, the edge node and the Oculus viewer. The application will run to track objects not visible from the point of view of the user. The object is identified by the drone, elaborated by the edge node and projected in the Oculus screen to visualize the object AR artifacts in its exact position behind the obstacle. The drone platform features a user equipment (UE), a double compute node, stereo cameras, and a real-time kinematic system (RTK). First object detection is performed onboard, with AR images sent to an edge node for further 3D reconstruction. Oculus users receive augmented views of hidden objects and can send control commands back to the drone in the form of zoom or camera move requests, directly using the Oculus commands.

FIGURE 58. DEMO 1 FINAL SETUP A) APPLICATION USE CASE, B) APPLICATION WORKFLOW, C) DRONE PLATFORM, D) DOUBLE RADIO ACCESS FOR HANDOVER TRIGGERED BY MAS

The network includes the drone UE connected to the Accelleran RAN, and one or two radio base stations for triggering the handover. Latency deviations are managed across different optimization layers. Single-domain real-time recovery is achieved via in-band control, while multiple-domain near-real-time recovery is triggered by MAS, utilizing RIC telemetry. SMO ensures non-real-time, quasi-hitless recovery through MAS predictions and handover mechanisms. Runtime MAS secure attestation will be enforced utilizing the latest features of the SecAAS software components.

The drone platform comprises autonomous quadcopters with dual on-board companion computers. These include an x86-NVIDIA hybrid architecture featuring a Jetson Orin NX and an Intel NUC, alongside

a Pixhawk 6X Flight Control Unit (FCU). The platform's PX4 software stack and ROS2 framework support advanced functionalities like LiDAR-based sensing and optimized energy usage.

Key features and component integrations include the deployment of network functions, service assurance, and re-optimization at various layers. MAS integrates a traffic prediction model trained on real-time data to maintain end-to-end delay within acceptable ranges. During handover or service migration, new MAS agents deploy RL models optimized for path delays.

Integration policies aim at emphasizing a coherent storyline, limiting unnecessary sub-components to simplify the demo's execution. Agreement on components and sub-components must be finalized to ensure seamless integration, with late changes discouraged due to their complexity. Components not active in Demo 1 may be included in standalone PoCs.

Integration milestones focus on enhanced edge applications and drone platforms leveraging optimized service layers. Monitoring data from RAN telemetry, including signal quality indicators and UE distance, supports predictive handover management. MAS and IML integration with SMO enable proactive traffic and service management.

6.1.1. Goal of the demonstrator

In this demonstrator, we assess an efficient and nearly real-time functionality of a 6G network including the RAN and the metro packet-optical network, fed by the distributed, intelligent Multi-Agent System (MAS). The MAS is applied to the end-to-end Augmented Reality (AR) service requiring low latency. Before the MAS agents are bootstrapped and ready to run, an initial stage validates the agent authenticity, leveraging D-MUTRA, a novel blockchain-based, platform agnostic mutual remote attestation scheme. This initial agent validation does not degrade the perceived zero latency AR demonstration KPI, being carried out prior to the effective execution of the MAS agents. Noticeably, this pre-run validation is representative of real use cases as remote attestations of platforms or software would induce a severe bottleneck latency for instant start payloads. The following description covers both initial (cold) MAS agent validation step and the (hot) running demonstration of the zero-latency perceived AR demonstration.

The preliminary D6G network solution seamlessly integrates two key components: i) pervasive In-band Network Telemetry (INT) agents, leveraging the capabilities of P4-based components in different networks and technological domains; and ii) multi-flow routing agents to dynamically adapt the network resources based on observed traffic patterns. In the RAN domain, it exploits the near real-time controller configurability, while in the packet-optical domain, multi-path flow routing policies are enforced within the packet nodes, aiming to ensure optimal Quality of Service (QoS) performance. Consequently, the network re-optimization to satisfy end-to-end latency is orchestrated by a diverse set of agents, each receiving real-time telemetry data from both the RAN and the metro-optical network, thanks to latency metadata offered by programmable P4 switches implemented in D6G.As a summary, the aim of the demo is to show all the DESIRE6G service assurance layers: the assurance scaling at the programmable data plane, the assurance scaling at the MAS level, the assurance scaling at the SMO level. The high-level execution plans are summarized in the following table:

TABLE 16. DEMO 1 INTELLIGENT AND RESILIENT VR/AR APPLICATIONS WITH PERCEIVED ZERO LATENCY WORKFLOWS

Workflow	Assurance type	Involved key components	Description	KPI
Steady state	Service assurance	SMO, IML, Monitoring, SecAAS		Application KPI (end-to-end latency, bandwidth, reliability)
Workflow1	Data plane assurance	P4 In-band control	Latency anomalies occurring at the data plane, recovered by in-band control	In-network programmability reaction time KPI

Workflow2		Pervasive monitoring, MAS, IML	Latency anomalies at the RAN, recovered thanks to MAS prediction (handover or scaling)	MAS KPIs IML KPIs
Workflow3		Pervasive monitoring, MAS, IML, SMO	Latency anomalies at the application containers, not recoverable using the network, recovered by the SMO and IML	SMO KPIs Serverless KPIs

At the time of writing, the full and detailed workflows of the demo are under discussion and will be finalized in 2025 Q1. Final integration will take place in 2025 Q2. Final demo executions and results are expected to be carried out in 2025 Q3-Q4.

6.2. Demo 2 Real-time Digital Twins

To meet the project goals and validate the KPIs, Demo 2 aims to integrate all the macro-components and technologies. This section details the finalized execution plan for Demo 2, including workflows, deployment strategies, and integration policies.

The first extension for Demo 2 involves creating a multi-domain federation environment that spans multiple D6G and non-D6G administrative domains (i.e., SMOs with local computing, networking, and storage infrastructure). All domains will integrate the DLT-based federation feature to enable secure, dynamic, and efficient orchestration of the DT service. Specifically, the final scenario (illustrated in Figure 59) will include three independent, heterogeneous domains. Each domain will run a blockchain node

directly connected to its respective SMO, forming a peer-to-peer blockchain network. A smart contract containing the federation procedures will be deployed on the blockchain, acting as a distributed authority for managing the federation process (refer to D3.1 for further details). The roles of the domains in this scenario will be as follows:

- **Consumer domain (red):** This domain corresponds to the Year 2 demo setup, enhanced with new components and infrastructure improvements detailed in the following paragraphs. It will act as the consumer, requesting federation to migrate or extend certain robotic functionalities within the DT service to other domains due to resource limitations.
- **Provider domain #1 (blue):** A D6G provider domain responsible for managing a deterministic transport network with PREOF-DetNet functionality. It will provide a reliable service connectivity between the consumer and provider domain #2.
- **Provider domain #2 (green):** A non-D6G provider domain leveraging the PREDICT-6G project platform [27]. It represents a heterogeneous domain and will deploy the requested AF of the DT service to fulfil the consumer domain requirements. Pre-established connectivity will exist between provider domains #1 and #2.

FIGURE 59. DEMO 2 FINAL SETUP

The demo will start with the consumer domain running the DT service as implemented in the Year 2 demo. A MAS agent will be pre-deployed to monitor DT service performance and ensure that the KPIs

are met. Then, we will simulate a resource saturation event on the edge server hosting the main applications of the DT service, causing the service to malfunction. The MAS agent will identify the problem and notify the SMO at the highest layer. Since no additional resources are available at the D6G site for redeployment, the SMO of the consumer domain will trigger a federation request to offload the affected application of the DT service to another domain. This federated service will require deploying the necessary application and establishing inter-domain connectivity to enable app-to-app communication. Using the DLT federation functionality, the domains will discover each other, negotiate federation terms, and securely exchange the required information to integrate the end-to-end service. This process will establish two federations between the consumer and the providers: one to access the deterministic transport network and another to deploy the requested application as part of the DT service.

The second extension will focus on upgrading the wireless connectivity infrastructure of the Year 2 demo scenario by replacing Wi-Fi with 5G technology, leveraging its key advantages such as ultra-low latency and enhanced reliability. The robot will be equipped with a UE that provides connectivity towards the 5G SA network available at the 5TONIC testbed, as described in D5.1.

Finally, the last extension of the demo will focus on the integration of the SOL and vAccel components to optimize an AI-driven application within the DT system. Specifically, we plan to develop and implement an additional computer vision application for monocular depth estimation, which will calculate object distances based on camera feeds from the robot. The SOL component will be utilized to enhance the efficiency of the AI model by leveraging its capabilities for neural network optimization, ensuring reduced latency and increased throughput during compilation. Meanwhile, the vAccel component will enable remote hardware acceleration by offloading computationally intensive tasks to dedicated hardware in remote or cloud environments. This will enhance execution performance, ensure real-time responsiveness, and reduce the computational load on the robot onboard resources.

To maintain a coherent storyline, the integration policies focus on eliminating redundant sub-components to streamline demo execution and minimize complexity. A final agreement on the components and sub-components is required to prevent last-minute modifications that could disrupt integration. Components not featured in Demo 2 may still be validated through standalone PoCs.

The detailed workflows for the demo are currently under discussion and are expected to be finalized by Q1 2025. The integration phase is planned for Q2 2025, with final demo execution and results anticipated in Q3-Q4 2025.

7. Updated data set collection

This section outlines the final datasets to be generated or utilized in developing the DESIRE6G components and PoCs, as initially defined in D5.1 [1]. It extends the initial descriptions with a focus on the the data collection process and outlining any updates to the attributes or structure of the datasets. Table 16 consolidates all datasets, linking them to their respective components or PoCs/Demos with references to their sources in Zenodo, where they will be progressively uploaded and made publicly available by the end of the project.

TABLE 17. DESIRE6G OVERVIEW OF UPDATED DATA SET ATTRIBUTES

Dataset	Associated component	Associated PoC/Demo	Source link
ML-based assisted SLA decomposition	SMO	None	https://zenodo.org/records/13837936
Elastic scaling	MAS	None	https://zenodo.org/records/13838059
Packet-based time series	None	Demo 1	https://zenodo.org/records/14526194
Baseline performance and MAS reaction to network anomalies	MAS, AR App, Telemetry Collector	Demo 1	https://zenodo.org/records/13259574
Digital Twin App	DT App	Demo 2	https://zenodo.org/records/14447162
DLT Network Transactions	SMO, MAS	PoC: Deployment of Secure Machine Learning Pipelines for Near-Real-Time Control of 6G Network Services, PoC: DLT-Mutual Remote	https://zenodo.org/records/14447544

		Attestation for MAS agents for platform-agnostic spontaneous zero touch authentication	
RIS application at EDGE nodes	None	PoC: ML model for RIS configuration prediction based on FL	https://zenodo.org/records/12731273

7.1. ML-based Assisted SLA Decomposition

7.1.1. General Dataset Description

The dataset is synthetic, generated to emulate admission control information and performance characteristics of network services in a multi-domain environment. An analytic model is used to create data (ground truth) for three domains. Each sample represents a partial SLA for a domain, characterized by a tuple of performance metrics (delay and throughput). SLA acceptance decisions (red-deny, green-accept) are influenced by network utilization, load, and other domain-specific constraints.

Figure 60a shows the response for admission controls of the ground truth model, where the dark green, light green, orange, light red and dark red regions correspond to an acceptance probability greater than 0.99, 0.9, 0.5, 0.1 and 0.01, respectively. Figure 60b depicts the sampled points in the dataset, where the green dots represent accepted requests and red dots rejected ones.

FIGURE 60. GROUND TRUTH AND SAMPLE POINTS.

7.1.2. Attributes, Variable Type and Description

TABLE 18.. ML-BASED ASSISTED SLA DECOMPOSITION ATTRIBUTES, VARIABLE TYPE AND DESCRIPTION

Attribute	Variable Type	Description
Delay	Float	Represents the delay requirement of the SLA.
Throughput	Float	Represents the throughput requirement of the SLA.
Acceptance	Bool	Indicates whether the SLA is accepted (1) or rejected (0) based on domain controllers.
Domain Id	Integer	Identifies the domain to which the partial SLA belongs.

7.2. Elastic Scaling

7.2.1. General Dataset Description

The dataset contains vehicular traffic data collected in Turin, Italy, spanning January to October 2020. It contains vehicle arrival data at over 100 locations, sampled in 5-minute intervals, which were

interpolated where data was missing. Five locations with representative traffic patterns were selected, see Figure 61, representing Points of Presence (PoPs) in the dataset. Vehicle arrivals were modelled as a time-varying Poisson process, using the recorded traffic intensities as arrival rates. This dataset is leveraged to evaluate a Cellular Vehicle-to-Network (C-V2N) application scenario, focusing on real-time task placement and resource scaling decisions across multiple PoPs in a metropolitan area.

FIGURE 61. VEHICULAR TRAFFIC DATASET OF TURIN.

7.2.2. Attributes, Variable Type and Description

TABLE 19. ELASTIC SCALING, VARIABLE TYPE AND DESCRIPTION

Attribute	Variable type	Description
Pop ID	Integer	Identifies the Point of Presence where a vehicle arrives.
Vehicle Arrival Time	Timestamp	The time of vehicle arrival at a PoP, modelled by Poisson processes.

7.3. Packet-based Time Series

7.3.1. General Dataset Description

This dataset contains the collected queuing delay values from a Juniper router, that is inserted in the middle of the processing pipeline of a P4 software switch as shown in Figure 62. The purpose is to use a P4 software switch with In-band Network Telemetry with a real queuing behaviour, as the software switch cannot properly simulate the delay that happens due to congesting the output queues of a physical interface. The collection method is done according to the setup shown in Figure 62 and is repeated five times to eliminate any randomness in the results. The Spirent Test Center generates traffic that goes to the software P4 NIKSS switch (eBPF implementation) which then gets forwarded to the Juniper router through a 2Gbps port which then gets forwarded back to the P4 switch through the 1Gbps port, effectively emulating a hardware queue within the processing pipeline of the P4 switch.

FIGURE 62. THE TESTBED USED TO COLLECT THE PACKET BASED DELAY TIME SERIES

The discrepancy in the data rate between the upstream and downstream ports is used to create congestion at the 1Gbps downstream port. In this way, when the traffic rate is close to 1Gbps, any burst will cause packets to enter the queue and to start to experience additional delay.

7.3.2. Attributes, Variable Type and Description

TABLE 20. PACKET-BASED TIME ATTRIBUTES, VARIABLE TYPE AND DESCRIPTION

Attribute	Type	Description
Experiment time	Variable Integer	a variable plotted on the x axis indicates the time in the experiment, always starts at 0 reported in milliseconds
Queuing Delay	Variable Integer	This variable is plotted on the y axis and represent the queuing delay experienced at the Juniper router as a function of the experiment time and the Baseline Traffic (including the Bursty Traffic) reported in microseconds

Baseline Traffic	Constant Integer	Baseline traffic kept constant for the duration of multiple runs of a single experiment. While it is varied among different experiments. Reported in Mbps
Burst Traffic	Constant Float	Set to be a percentage of the baseline traffic that is added to the baseline traffic at the middle of the experiment run. Reported as a percentage.

7.4. Baseline Performance and MAS reaction to network anomalies in Demo 1

7.4.1. General Dataset Description

This dataset is collected during the runs of demo 1 for monitoring end to end latency of a terminal accessing an Augmented Reality application located on an edge server. The network has two segments, a RAN segment and a PDP segment. The INT header is inserted at the UE to collect the subsequent latency information of the network segments. This information is fed to the MAS to react to network anomalies. The data set also contains a packet capture of the Telemetry Collector, and of the communication with the MAS for policy enforcement.

7.4.2. Attributes, Variable Type and Description

TABLE 21. BASELINE PERFORMANCE AND MAS REACTION TO NETWORK ANOMALIES ATTRIBUTES, VARIABLE TYPE AND DESCRIPTION

Attribute	Type	Description
Experiment time	Variable Integer	a variable plotted on the x axis indicates the time in the experiment, always starts at 0
RAN Latency	Variable Integer	This variable is plotted on the y axis and represent the RAN latency experienced at the RAN segment in microseconds.

PDP Latency	Variable Integer	This variable is plotted on the y axis and represent the PDP latency experienced at the PDP segment reported in microseconds.
Total Latency	Variable Integer	Equals the combined latency of RAN and PDP. Reported in microseconds.

7.5. Digital Twin App

7.5.1. General Dataset Description

The Digital Twin App dataset will be produced by the DT app for the Unitree Go1 quadruped robot as part of the Demo 2, including data on various aspects of robotic control and sensors. It will be provided in ROS bag⁴ format, a file format used in Robot Operating System (ROS) to store messages exchanged between nodes. This format allows the capture and offline replay of system data, enabling analysis, debugging, and experimentation without requiring a live robot setup.

Data collection will be performed during the normal operation of the DT app. A Docker container will automate the process by capturing all messages exchanged in the ROS system between the edge server running the DT app and the physical robot in real-time, exporting the data to a ROS bag file.

To enhance usability, the dataset will include an additional Docker container with a preconfigured ROS installation. This container eliminates the need for installing additional software, such as specific operating system versions or ROS dependencies, and provides a straightforward way to replay the data offline for analysis. Moreover, the container will include GUI support and the ROS visualization tool (RViz)⁵, enabling users to graphically visualize the data, as shown in Figure 63.

⁴ <https://wiki.ros.org/rosbag>

⁵ <https://wiki.ros.org/rviz>

FIGURE 63. EXAMPLE VISUALIZATION OF LIDAR DATA CAPTURED IN ROS BAG FOR THE DT APP DATASET

7.5.2. Attributes, Variable Type and Description

The attributes of this dataset remain as specified in D5.1 [1], where detailed descriptions and variable types are provided.

7.6. DLT Network Transactions

7.6.1. General Dataset Description

The DLT Network Transactions dataset provides a comprehensive log of all transactions within the DESIRE6G DLT solution, covering both service federation and MAS security aspects, as detailed in D5.1. It serves as a valuable resource for analysing DLT network behaviour, detecting anomalies, and ensuring data integrity. This dataset will be produced during the development of DLT-based service federation feature of the SMO and the security mechanisms for the MAS (i.e., VXLAN key exchanges for secure inter-agent communication, targeted for Demo Augmented Reality (AR) with Perceived Zero Latency, and mutual remote attestation to ensure agent integrity, targeted for Demo Digital Twin.

Data collection will be performed on a private Ethereum-based blockchain network using the Geth⁶ framework with PoA (Proof-of-Authority) consensus algorithm. A Docker container will automate the process by monitoring transactions in real-time, including interactions with smart contracts, and exporting the data to a CSV file. Multiple tests and repeated executions will be conducted for each scenario, generating sufficient transaction activity to simulate realistic conditions.

7.6.2. Attributes, Variable Type and Description

TABLE 22. DLT NETWORK TRANSACTIONS ATTRIBUTES, VARIABLE TYPE AND DESCRIPTION

Attribute	Variable type	Description
Block Number	Integer	The number of the block containing the transaction
Timestamp	Datetime	The date and time when the block containing the transaction was created
Transaction Hash	String	A unique identifier (hash) for the transaction
From	String	The address of the sender who initiated the transaction
To	String	The address of the address of the recipient or the contract being interacted with
Value	Float	The amount of Ether transferred in the transaction
Gas	Integer	The computational effort required to process the transaction or execute a smart contract
Gas Price	Float	The cost the sender is willing to pay for each unit of computational effort (gas), expressed in Gwei
Nonce	Integer	The number of transactions made by the sender prior to this one

⁶ <https://geth.ethereum.org/>

Status	Boolean	The status of the transaction: <i>1</i> for success, <i>0</i> for failure
Contract Address	String	The address of the deployed smart contract if this transaction created one, or <i>None</i> otherwise
Contract Name	String	The name of the smart contract if the transaction interacts with a known contract, or <i>None</i> otherwise
Function Name	String	The name of the function called in the smart contract, if applicable; otherwise, <i>None</i>

7.7. ML assister RIS configuration at EDGE nodes

Building upon the dataset discussed in Section 5.5 of D5.1 [1], we have enhanced the resolution by increasing the range of label choices. For completeness and clarity, we have adequately modified the description of the dataset and its attributes, along with the new updates.

7.7.1. General Dataset Description

The dataset contains Channel State Information of RIS assisted wireless environments, together with configuration indexes as labels. Specifically, it provides realizations of the channels \mathbf{h} and \mathbf{g} from a single antenna transmitter to the RIS and from the RIS to the single antenna receiver, respectively, see Figure 64. Each realization is labelled by the ‘optimal RIS configuration’ that maximizes the receiver’s rate.

FIGURE 64. RIS ENVIRONMENTS

The ‘optimal RIS configuration’ is computed by choosing the best over N possible choices, which we refer to as *quantization index*. Each choice corresponds to a ‘representative RIS configuration’. Given channels \mathbf{h} and \mathbf{g} , the best choice y is the one that corresponds to the representative RIS configuration yielding the maximum achievable rate computed by considering the commonly used Shannon’s formula. Thus, associated with each pair \mathbf{h}, \mathbf{g} the label y is assigned as the ‘optimal RIS configuration’. The number N ranges from 2 to 100. Therefore, technically, we have one dataset for each N , which in turn results in 99 data sets.

The target group for this dataset can typically be engineers and researchers from wireless communications, signal processing, and machine learning. The rate-maximization by tuning the reflecting elements of RISs in a RIS setting is a combinatorial optimization problem, and therefore to compute an approximate configuration for the reflecting elements in an efficient manner is of crucial importance in practice. In this respect, the above dataset can be used to train a neural network for efficiently computing a reasonable configuration for reflecting elements.

The dataset consists of 50,000 samples splitted heterogeneously across 4 RIS environments indexed by $r \in \{1,2,3,4\}$.

7.7.2. Attributes, Variable Type and Description

The detailed attributes of the dataset are outlined in the table below:

TABLE 23. HETEROGENEOUS RIS ENVIRONMENTS ATTRIBUTES, VARIABLE TYPE AND DESCRIPTION

Attribute	Variable type	Description
Channel: Transmitter-RIS (\mathbf{h}^r)	Complex vectors of length N^r	Channel between a single antenna transmitter and the RIS in the RIS environment r .
Chanel: RIS-Receiver (\mathbf{g}^r)	Complex vectors of length N^r	Channel between the RIS and a single antenna receiver in the RIS environment r .
Quantization index (N)	An integer from 2 to 100	N is a parameter that represents a level of quantization used when computing the 'optimal RIS configuration'. In the original dataset (see Section 5.5 of D5.1), $N = 2$.
Optimal RIS configuration y^r	An integer form 0 to $N - 1$	Represent the index that corresponds to the 'representative RIS configuration' which yields the maximum rate.

8. Tests Definition and results

A set of tests have been defined following a template agreed among all the partners involved in the software component release, the integration and the validation activities.

8.1. Definition of Tests for Use Case Validation

The main tests have been conceived and designed to address the two main use case and the two integrated demos. Here we refer to the definition of tests related to the preliminary demonstrations (i.e., Demo1 on AR and Demo2 on DT) to be performed in Y2. It is expected that the tests will be run and assessed during the execution of task T5.3, beginning in July 2024, until the release of this deliverable (D5.2).

8.1.1. Definition of Tests for Demo 1 Y2

Test Name	Type of Test	D6G Test Inventory ID	Responsible Partner(s)
Baseline Performance Evaluation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inter-component Integration test 	T5.11 [WP5.Release1.x]	CNIT, SSSA, NVIDIA; UPC, ACC
Testbed	Demo/PoC	Involved components	Test
ARNO, UPC testbed	Demo 2 Y2	AR app, P4 Telemetry Collector, Telemetry Agent, Accelleran Baseline RAN	Preliminary
Description of the test			
Main function	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Evaluate the performance of the preliminary AR app under normal operational conditions. 		

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evaluate the capability of the pervasive telemetry and the MAS to collect and exchange telemetry results related to AR app in real time • Evaluate the capability of the RAN to process UE uplink traffic
Test requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The monitored application is the AR app developed by CNIT, the traffic under monitoring are streaming UDP flows related to videos processed by the app components • Telemetry Reports are generated only for the flows being monitored • Additional traffic may be present after initial check
External tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Traffic Generator and Analyzer (Spirent N4U) • InfluxDB for exporting metrics • Grafana for dynamic visualization
Measurement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Metrics relevant to application traffic, including bandwidth, delay, jitter, and packet loss
Related Project KPIs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • End-to-end latency, data rate
Test execution	
Initial setup/assumptions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The RAN is deployed • The P4 switches are deployed, and flow entries are configured • The App is activated and generates traffic.
Steps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 0. Activate the RAN 1. Activate the P4 switches and the collector 2. Activate the MAS 3. Activate the APP 4. Send the flow entry configurations to the switches 5. Check that the traffic is flowing from source to destination 6. Check the steady values of latency measured in all the segments 7. Activate Spirent traffic (with no issues on congestion/latency) 8. Check and measure the output traffic to the MAS agent 9. Check the MAS reaction to steady state (should be with no reply) 10. Collect all the steady state measurements and statistics

Test Name	Type of Test	D6G Test Inventory ID	Responsible Partner(s)

Telemetry Collector and Agent Scalability Test	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inter-component Integration test 	T5.12 [WP5.Release1.x]	CNIT, SSSA, NVIDIA; UPC
Testbed	Demo/PoC	Involved components	Test
ARNO, UPC testbed	Demo 1 Y2	AR app, P4 Telemetry Collector, Telemetry Agent, Accelleran Baseline RAN	Preliminary
Description of the test			
Main function	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Evaluate the capability of the collector to provide traffic data telemetry to the MAS regardless the current throughput of the programmable network Evaluate the capability of the P4 collector to monitor a high number of flows Compute the scalability limit of the double stage P4 collector depending on the considered P4 backend 		
Test requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The monitored application is the AR app developed by CNIT, the traffic under monitoring is a streaming UDP flow (video streaming) The network conceives P4 switches (BMv2 releases) enforcing INT or postcard telemetry The Reports are generated only for the considered flows under monitoring 		
External tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Traffic Generator and Analyzer (Spirent N4U) InfluxDB for exporting metrics Grafana for dynamic visualization 		

Measurement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Metrics relevant Monitoring system including bandwidth efficiency, reaction and processing times.
Related Project KPIs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Component latency, data rate, CPU rate, number of sustainable flows, dimension of the network
Test execution	
Initial setup/assumptions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All the P4 switches are deployed and flow entries related to telemetry activation are sent to the switches and to the Collector • The Collector runs in Correlation mode (performs data aggregation and correlation to produce 1s samples of telemetry statistics to be sent to the MAS agent) • The Spirent N4U is programmed to generate a number of different flows (100Mb/s each) related to UDP traffic with different src and dst ports
Steps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 0. Send the AR traffic along the PDP network 1. Switch on the Spirent traffic connections 2. Check traffic throughput and CPU level of the P4 switches (if software) 3. Wait 30 seconds to achieve steady state conditions 4. Measure CPU and RAM utilization at the P4 collector stage 1 level (P4 pipeline) and at stage 2 (internal agent) 5. Check and measure the output traffic to the MAS agent
Test results	

13	1.421867009	10.0.1.10	10.0.5.10	INT (INT_Report)	64
14	1.520627208	10.10.10.10	11.11.11.11	INT (INT_Summary)	64
15	1.520417942	10.0.1.10	10.0.5.10	INT (INT_Report)	64
16	1.610355574	10.0.1.10	10.0.5.10	INT (INT_Report)	64
17	1.709983370	10.0.1.10	10.0.5.10	INT (INT_Report)	64
18	1.820513227	10.0.1.10	10.0.5.10	INT (INT_Report)	64
19	1.960124505	10.0.1.10	10.0.5.10	INT (INT_Report)	64
20	2.070273284	10.0.1.10	10.0.5.10	INT (INT_Report)	64
21	2.190610404	10.0.1.10	10.0.5.10	INT (INT_Report)	64
22	2.290860940	10.0.1.10	10.0.5.10	INT (INT_Report)	64
23	2.400845869	10.0.1.10	10.0.5.10	INT (INT_Report)	64
24	2.540061255	10.0.1.10	10.0.5.10	INT (INT_Report)	64
25	2.640528162	10.0.1.10	10.0.5.10	INT (INT_Report)	64
26	2.770288149	10.0.1.10	10.0.5.10	INT (INT_Report)	64
27	2.850533122	10.0.1.10	10.0.5.10	INT (INT_Report)	64
28	2.970646132	10.0.1.10	10.0.5.10	INT (INT_Report)	64

▶ Frame 1: 64 bytes on wire (512 bits), 64 bytes captured (512 bits) on interface eth40, id 1

- ▶ Ethernet II, Src: 56:1e:10:00:01:10 (56:1e:10:00:01:10), Dst: 56:1e:10:00:11:01 (56:1e:10:00:11:01)
- ▼ Internet Protocol Version 4, Src: 10.0.1.10, Dst: 10.0.5.10
 - 0100 = Version: 4
 - 0101 = Header Length: 20 bytes (5)
 - ▶ Differentiated Services Field: 0x00 (DSCP: CS0, ECN: Not-ECT)
 - Total Length: 50
 - Identification: 0x0001 (1)
 - ▶ Flags: 0x00
 - ...0 0000 0000 0000 = Fragment Offset: 0
 - Time to Live: 60
 - Protocol: Unknown (253)
 - Header Checksum: 0x63bb [correct]
 - [Header checksum status: Good]
 - [Calculated Checksum: 0x63bb]
 - Source Address: 10.0.1.10
 - Destination Address: 10.0.5.10
- ▼ InBand Telemetry Data
 - messageType: 0 (INT_Report)
 - originalProtocol: 17
 - delayRAN: 8887
 - delayPDP: 8636
 - pathId: 1

FIGURE 65. PACKET CAPTURE AT THE P4 COLLECTOR THAT SHOWS THE SUMMARY OF 16 INT REPORTS

Test Name	Type of Test	D6G Test Inventory ID	Responsible Partner(s)
Reaction of the system to network anomaly: congestion case	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inter-component Integration test 	T5.13 [WP5.Release1.x]	CNIT, SSSA, NVIDIA; UPC, ACC
Testbed	Demo/PoC	Involved components	Test
ARNO, UPC testbed	Demo 1 Y2	AR app, P4 Telemetry Collector, Telemetry Agent, Accelleran Baseline RAN	Preliminary
Description of the test			
Main function	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Evaluate the capability of the pervasive telemetry + the MAS to react promptly to anomalies induced in the network. In this test the anomaly is a congestion event occurring at one of the P4 switches of the PDP domain Measure the times of the components and the full loop reaction time 		
Test requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The monitored application is the AR app developed by CNIT, the traffic under monitoring is a streaming UDP flow (video streaming) The network conceives P4 switches (BMv2 releases) enforcing INT or postcard telemetry The Reports are generated only for the considered flows under monitoring 		
External tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Traffic Generator and Analyzer (Spirent N4U) InfluxDB for exporting metrics Grafana for dynamic visualization 		

Measurement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Latency variations due to congestion • Pervasive monitoring reaction time • MAS reaction time • Overall system reaction time and impact on the AR traffic
Related Project KPIs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 7.4
Test execution	
Initial setup/assumptions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All the P4 switches are deployed and flow entries related to telemetry activation are sent to the switches and to the Collector • The Collector runs in Correlation mode (performs data aggregation and correlation to produce 1s samples of telemetry statistics to be sent to the MAS agent) • The Spirent N4U is programmed to generate a number of different flows (100Mb/s each) related to UDP traffic with different src and dst ports • AR is flowing as baseline conditions
Steps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 0. Activate all the subsystems to run in steady state 1. Check that the traffic is flowing from source to destination and steady state parameters at collector and MAS 2. Activate Spirent traffic (with significant issues on congestion/latency) 3. Check and measure the congestion impact in terms of latency and queue length at the involved nodes 4. Check the MAS reaction (it should react with a suggested change) 5. Measure the time to inform the MAS about the anomaly 6. Measure the time needed by the MAS to perform the re-optimization suggestion 7. Measure the re-optimization enforcement time 8. Check that e2e latency is recovered 9. Evaluate the overall recovery time (collector+MAS+enforcement)

Test results

The Figure 66 shows the latency of the monitored flow on two paths (primary path on the top, and the backup path on the bottom) due to simulated congestion at the RAN segment.

The MAS has no backup path for the RAN so it configures the PDP traffic to go over the optical bypass resulting in a PDP latency of around 1ms.

FIGURE 66. LATENCY OF THE MONITORED FLOW ON TWO PATHS

The Figure 67 shows an increase in the latency on the primary path rising above the threshold of 25ms, so the MAS configure the monitored flow to go over the backup path in PDP.

FIGURE 67. INCREASE IN THE LATENCY ON THE PRIMARY PATH

The figure below shows an example of a policy deployed by the MAS to reroute the monitored flow of the AR application.

No.	Time	Source	Destination	Protocol	Length	Info
1	2024-07-10 12:01:17,227494	192.168.30.134	192.168.30.74	TCP	272	40522 → 8080 [PSH, ACK] Seq=1 Ack=1 Win=502 Len=206 TSval=1767651062 TSecr=1074951078 [TCP segment of a reassembled PDU]
2	2024-07-10 12:01:17,227707	192.168.30.134	192.168.30.74	HTTP/JSON	194	POST /QoS HTTP/1.1, JavaScript Object Notation (application/json)
3	2024-07-10 12:01:17,230744	192.168.30.74	192.168.30.134	TCP	263	8080 → 40522 [PSH, ACK] Seq=1 Ack=335 Win=507 Len=197 TSval=1074951082 TSecr=1767651062 [TCP segment of a reassembled PDU]
4	2024-07-10 12:01:17,231272	192.168.30.74	192.168.30.134	HTTP/JSON	88	HTTP/1.1 200 OK, JavaScript Object Notation (application/json)
5	2024-07-10 12:01:17,277981	192.168.30.74	10.0.8.3	TCP	269	36708 → 8080 [PSH, ACK] Seq=1 Ack=1 Win=502 Len=203 TSval=3757973827 TSecr=2645164741 [TCP segment of a reassembled PDU]
6	2024-07-10 12:01:17,278053	192.168.30.74	10.0.8.3	HTTP/JSON	123	[POST /policy HTTP/1.1, JavaScript Object Notation (application/json)]
7	2024-07-10 12:01:17,324615	10.0.8.3	192.168.30.74	TCP	238	8080 → 36708 [PSH, ACK] Seq=1 Ack=261 Win=85 Len=172 TSval=2645164787 TSecr=3757973827 [TCP segment of a reassembled PDU]
8	2024-07-10 12:01:17,334870	10.0.8.3	192.168.30.74	HTTP	71	HTTP/1.1 200 OK (text/html)

```

> Frame 6: 123 bytes on wire (984 bits), 123 bytes captured (984 bits)
> Ethernet II, Src: fa:16:3e:42:44:73 (fa:16:3e:42:44:73), Dst: Tp-LinkT_07:88:cb (50:3e:aa:07:88:cb)
> Internet Protocol Version 4, Src: 192.168.30.74, Dst: 10.0.8.3
> Transmission Control Protocol, Src Port: 36708, Dst Port: 8080, Seq: 204, Ack: 1, Len: 57
> [2 Reassembled TCP Segments (260 bytes): #5(203), #6(57)]
>
> Hypertext Transfer Protocol
JavaScript Object Notation: application/json
  Object
    Member: paths
      Object
        Member: p1
          [Path with value: /paths/p1:0]
          [Member with value: p1:0]
          Number value: 0
          Key: p1
          [Path: /paths/p1]
        Member: p2
          [Path with value: /paths/p2:0]
          [Member with value: p2:0]
          Number value: 0
          Key: p2
          [Path: /paths/p2]
        Member: p3
          [Path with value: /paths/p3:100]
          [Member with value: p3:100]
          Number value: 100
          Key: p3
          [Path: /paths/p3]
      Key: paths
      [Path: /paths]
    Member: flow_id
      [Path with value: /flow_id:10]
      [Member with value: flow_id:10]
      String value: 10
      Key: flow_id
      [Path: /flow_id]
    
```

Test outcome comments

In this test we had two scenarios, the first one a congestion is simulated at the RAN segment causing the RAN latency to rise to around 21ms and total latency to rise above the set threshold of 25ms so the MAS configures a backup path in the PDP segment, so the total latency remains within the set bounds. In the second figure, the congestion happened at the PDP causing its latency to rise to about 13ms, so the MAS responds by setting the traffic to go over the configured backup path in the PDP to reduce the PDP latency back to around 6ms.

8.1.2. Definition of Tests for Demo 2 Y2

Test Name	Type of Test	D6G Test Inventory ID	Responsible Partner(s)
Baseline Performance Evaluation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inter-component Integration test 	T5.1.4 [WP5.Release1.x]	UC3M, NUBIS, ELTE
Testbed	Demo/PoC	Involved components	Test
5TONIC	Demo 2 Y2	DT app, SMO (SO, DL, SC), IML (Local NFVO, NFR, UE2Service Mapper)	Preliminary
Description of the test			
Main function	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Evaluate the performance of the real-time DT system under normal operational conditions Evaluate the capability of the first releases of the SMO and IML to efficiently deploy the corresponding AFs/NFs for the DT service 		
Test requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The monitored application is the DT app developed by UC3M, the traffic under monitoring are streaming TCP flows (TCPROS layer for transporting ROS message data) Reports are generated only for the flows being monitored 		
External tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ROS message traffic analyzer (rospy client API) tcpdump for capturing and analyzing network traffic InfluxDB for exporting metrics Grafana for dynamic visualization 		
Measurement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Metrics relevant to application traffic, including bandwidth, delay, and jitter 		

Related Project KPIs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI7.2
Test execution	
Initial setup/assumptions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The robot is functional, and all system components are operational and interconnected • The D6G site is already registered in the SMO with an assigned ID, and the service graph for the DT service is uploaded and available in the Service Catalog
Steps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 0. Request service deployment of the DT app at the D6G site from the SO 1. Verify the correct deployment of AFs and NFs: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. The SO retrieves Service Graph from the SC and forwards it to the IML (Local NFVO) b. The IML deploys the AFs/NFs on the D6G site, pulling the corresponding container images from the DL c. The IML configure D6G header-based routing (NFR) between network function data plane components d. The IML configure UE2ServiceMapper data plane component 2. Verify the correct functionality of the DT app, which includes: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. The robot can be remotely controlled via the gesture control app b. The robot movements are accurately mirrored in real time within the Isaac Sim digital twin simulator c. Environmental mapping is successfully generated using SLAM algorithms d. The robot camera feed is correctly visualized 3. Monitor the end-to-end traffic data between the robot and the edge server at the D6G site 4. Check and measure metrics for relevant application data, such as control commands, joint states, LiDAR, and odometry

5. Request service termination from the SO

Test results

The Figure 68 shows the bandwidth usage of key topics monitored in the DT application under normal conditions. The data was collected using the *rostopic bw* command at each subscriber node, which measures the bandwidth consumed by a topic based on the received messages.

FIGURE 68. DEMO 2 Y2: BANDWIDTH UTILIZATION FOR DT APP TRAFFIC IN BASELINE POC

The figure 69 shows the RTT latency distribution for key topics monitored in the DT application under normal conditions. The data was collected using tcpdump to capture TCPROS traffic, as the rostopic CLI method was imprecise due to clock synchronization limitations in ROS. RTT latency was calculated as the time taken for a message to travel from the publisher to the subscriber and receive an acknowledgment (ACK), excluding retransmissions and duplicates. Jitter was measured as the variation in consecutive RTT latency values.

FIGURE 69. DEMO 2 Y2: RTT LATENCY DISTRIBUTION FOR DT APP TRAFFIC IN BASELINE POC

Test outcome comments

Successfully verified the integration and communication among D6G components within the 5TONIC environment, achieving E2E DT service deployment across the robot and the edge server.

The results show that the bandwidth requirements for the initial demo are generally low, with notable variation across ROS topics: control commands require 50 kbps, joint states 450 kbps, odometry 600 kbps, and LiDAR data consumes the most at 1.2 Mbps. This variation reflects the nature of the data, with sensor-intensive topics like LiDAR demanding far more bandwidth compared to lighter control or state-related information.

Latency measurements indicate that the 95th percentile latency is approximately 2.7 ms for control, joint states, and odometry topics, and 3.7 ms for the laser scan topic. Similarly, the 50th percentile latency is around 1.2 ms for control, joint states, and odometry, and 2.1 ms for the laser scan. The small difference between the 50th and 95th percentiles demonstrates minimal jitter, highlighting stable network conditions. Although the laser scan topic shows slightly higher latency and jitter due to its larger message size, this has less impact on system performance compared to the control and state-

related topics, where maintaining low latency is critical for real-time robot control and synchronization with its virtual replica.

Test Name	Type of Test	D6G Test Inventory ID	Responsible Partner(s)
Reaction of the system to network anomaly: congestion case	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inter-component Integration test 	T5.15 [WP5.Release1.x]	UC3M, NUBIS, ELTE
Testbed	Demo/PoC	Involved components	Test
5TONIC	Demo 2 Y2	DT app, SMO (SO, DL, SC), IML (Local NFVO, NFR, UE2Service Mapper), PPV-TM	Preliminary
Description of the test			
Main function	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Evaluate the performance of the DT system under network load, comparing results with and without the D6G traffic management solution 		
Test requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The monitored application is the DT app developed by UC3M, the traffic under monitoring are streaming TCP flows (TCPROS layer for transporting ROS message data) The reports are generated only for the considered flows under monitoring 		
External tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ROS message traffic analyzer (rospy client API) tcpdump for capturing and analyzing network traffic 		

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • InfluxDB for exporting metrics • Grafana for dynamic visualization
Measurement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Metrics relevant to application traffic, including bandwidth, delay, and jitter
Related Project KPIs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI7.1
Test execution	
Initial setup/assumptions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The robot is functional, and all system components are operational and interconnected • The D6G site is already registered in the SMO with an assigned ID, and the service graph for the DT service is uploaded and available in the Service Catalog • The distributed DT app is deployed on the D6G site and is flowing as baseline conditions • The end-to-end traffic data between the robot and the edge server at the D6G site is being monitored
Steps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Emulate a background NS with over 100 UE flows 2. Show the performance impact on the DT app 3. Trigger TM functionality to apply different policy that (i) guarantee performance isolation between services and users, and (ii) allocate higher guaranteed bandwidth to essential robot traffic in the DT NS 4. Show the restoration of normal DT service operation 5. Compare the results using the SoA solution versus the D6G traffic management solution
Test results	
<p>The Figure 70 shows the industrial traffic generated by the traffic generator server using the iperf tool. It emulates 100 UEs, with each represented as an individual TCP flow.</p>	

FIGURE 70. DEMO 2 Y2: GENERATED BACKGROUND TRAFFIC BANDWIDTH ON GRAFANA

The Figure 71 shows the TM policies applied by IML in the programmable switch to prioritize critical flows within the DT NS. The key parameters of the policy are as follows:

- **ns-id:** The service ID to which the policy applies.
- **assigned-user-ids:** List of user IDs belonging to the service where the policy is enforced.
- **min-bw:** Minimum guaranteed bandwidth in Kbps.
- **max-bw:** Maximum allowed bandwidth in Kbps.
- **elasticity:** A weight factor determining weighted resource sharing between min-bw and max-bw. Larger weights result in higher throughput allocation. Beyond max-bw, the service operates on a best-effort basis (i.e., if no congestion).

Within the DT NS:

- **UE ID 8472** represents the critical robot traffic, covering all traffic via the VXLAN tunnel (UDP port 8472) in the Kubernetes cluster between the edge server and the robot.

- UE ID 20000** represents non-essential robot traffic, generated as a separate background TCP flow. Please note that this approach was adopted for the initial demonstration because the programmable data plane cannot process text-based protocols like ROS. Filtering ROS traffic by TCP headers is also challenging because nodes are dynamically assigned random TCP ports at runtime, making it difficult to identify and isolate the traffic in advance. In the final demonstration, non-essential traffic (i.e., robot camera flows) will be isolated outside the VXLAN tunnel.

Within the background NS:

- UE IDs 20001-20100** represent 100 emulated users generating industrial traffic.

FIGURE 71. DEMO 2 Y2: TM POLICIES FOR CRITICAL TRAFFIC PRIORITIZATION IN THE DT SERVICE

Figure 72 illustrates the latency distribution of the application critical traffic under the network congestion scenario, with each essential flow from the DT service represented by a distinct color.

Figure 72-A presents the results of the state-of-the-art (SoA) solution without the D6G platform, while Figure 72 -B shows the results with the D6G platform managing the traffic of the DT system.

FIGURE 72. DEMO 2 Y2: LATENCY DISTRIBUTION FOR DT APP TRAFFIC UNDER NETWORK CONGESTION – COMPARISON OF SOA (A) AND D6G PLATFORM (B)

Test outcome comments

Since the background NS initially used the same policy as the DT NS, with a basic tail-drop mechanism, it led to network congestion. This caused performance degradation in the applications, particularly affecting robot control and DT synchronization. At this point, the IML triggered the TM feature in the programmable switch to prioritize the important flows related to the DT NS. Different TM policies were applied (see Figure 71) to ensure performance isolation between services and users, with higher bandwidth allocated to critical robot traffic. As a result, the robot continued to function properly, as it would under normal conditions.

At the 95th percentile, we can observe that the SoA solution shows a latency of approximately 158 ms, which significantly exceeds the operational requirements for the DT use case. Please note that in this scenario involving the high-level remote control of a mobile quadruped robot, latencies exceeding 100 ms will significantly degrade system performance, leading to poor Quality-of-Experience (QoE) for the remote operator and increasing the risk of potential crashes (see the Demo 2 Y2 video⁷). In contrast,

⁷ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=E5fGB1bzGsE&t=106s>

the D6G platform effectively prioritizes the robot critical traffic, reducing latency to approximately 12 ms. This optimization ensures normal system operation despite the background traffic.

9. Conclusion

This deliverable marks a significant step forward in the project's efforts to validate key technologies and concepts that will shape the future of 6G networks. Through a combination of global, local, and federated testbeds, the project has successfully integrated and demonstrated the functionality of core components and proof-of-concept (PoC) use cases. These activities have provided valuable insights into the challenges and opportunities related to deploying advanced network functionalities across diverse environments.

The initial demonstrations highlighted in this report confirmed the feasibility of achieving KPIs such as ultra-low latency, high reliability, and intelligent service orchestration. They also showcased the potential for integrating emerging technologies such as digital twins, augmented reality, and intelligent monitoring within a 6G framework.

The progress made so far lays a solid foundation for the project's next phase, which will involve refining these solutions, addressing any remaining challenges, and preparing for the final databases and demonstrations. Moving forward, DESIRE6G will continue to focus on improving the proposed solutions to meet the needs of future networks.

In summary, the results presented in this deliverable have demonstrated the potential of DESIRE6G to contribute meaningfully to the development of 6G next-generation networks, setting the stage for further advancements toward a fully operational 6G ecosystem.

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